

ROLE OF PATENTS IN DIFFUSION OF ENVIRONMENTALLY SOUND TECHNOLOGIES: INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

Dissertation

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This is to certify that the research that forms the basis of this Dissertation titled "**ROLE OF PATENTS IN DIFFUSION OF ENVIRONMENTALLY SOUND TECHNOLOGIES: INDIAN PERSPECTIVE**" is an original work carried out by me and has not been submitted anywhere else for the award of any degree.

I certify that, to the best of my knowledge, all sources of information and data have been fully acknowledged in the report.

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Role of Patents in Diffusion of Environmentally Sound Technologies: Indian Perspective

By Ayushman Kheterpal (1800065LLM)

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ABSTRACT

IPRs, in particular Patents, can be hurdle or opportunity based on the situation. Integrated factors other than strictness of Patent Regime are also important in Diffusion of ESTs which have been discussed in detail in the present research. International Legal framework plays a crucial role in ESTs diffusion into India. Major legal frameworks relevant for present research include Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1883; Patent Cooperation Treaty, 1970; WTO framework; TRIPS; UNFCCC; WIPO Green and SDGs. Policy and Legal framework of India are also closely intertwined with diffusion of ESTs, their relationship is discussed in the present research. Policy related to climate change and renewable energy is also discussed. In Indian Legal Dimension, Strict Criteria of Patentability, Compulsory Licensing, Patent Prosecution Highway, Commercial Working Data and Renewable Energy is discussed. Thereafter, detailed empirical research is carried out wherein, search query is determined for wind and solar power generation technologies, yearly trends are studied, and nationality of applicants are determined. Towards the end of this research, summary of the research work carried out has been stated and suggestions have been described.

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ABBREVIATIONS

1. CCMTs – Climate Change Mitigation Technologies
2. CEA – Central Energy Authority
3. CO₂ – Carbon di Oxide
4. ESTs – Environmentally Sound Technologies
5. EU – European Union
6. EPO – European Patent Office
7. FDI – Foreign Direct Investment
8. Forex – Foreign Exchange
9. FRAND – Fair Reasonable And Non Discriminatory
10. GATT – General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade
11. GHG – Green House Gas
12. GIS – Geographic Information System
13. GM – Genetically Modified
14. GMO – Genetically Modified Organism
15. ICTSD – International Centre for Trade and Sustainable Development (an independent non-profit organization based in Geneva)
16. INDC – Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (under UNFCCC Framework)
17. inPASS – Indian Patent Advanced Search System
18. IP – Intellectual Property
19. IPEA – International Preliminary Examining Authority
20. IPO – Indian Patent Office
21. IPR – Intellectual Property Right
22. ISA – International Searching Authority
23. ISR – International Search Report
24. JPPH – Japanese patent Prosecution Highway
25. LPG – Liberalization Privatization Globalization (Indian Economic Reforms of 1990s)
26. NP – National Phase
27. PCT – Patent Cooperation Treaty
28. PPH – Patent Prosecution Highway
29. PPP – Public Private Partnership
30. R&D – Research and Development
31. REC – Renewable Energy Certificates
32. RGO/RPO – Renewable Generation/Purchase Obligations
33. SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals
34. Solar PV – Solar Photo Voltaic
35. TKDL – Traditional Knowledge Digital Library
36. TRIPS – Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
37. UN – United Nations
38. UNEP – United Nations Environment Programme
39. UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
40. USA/US – United States of America
41. USPTO – United States Patent and Trademark Office
42. WIPO – World Intellectual Property Organization (an organ of UN situated in Geneva)
43. WTO – World Trade Organization

Role of Patents in Diffusion of Environmentally Sound Technologies: Indian Perspective

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of Research

The fundamental of this paper is based on the consideration that to tackle Climate Change while attaining Sustainable Development requires significant advancements in science and technology which is a capital-intensive process and thus, IPR Laws specifically Patent Laws have evolved to provide incentives to private and public researchers. However, Patent laws being nascent in their origin are not in coherence with even more nascent concept of Climate Change.

Climate Change is increasingly becoming a serious issue which if not tackled properly can cause serious natural disasters, weather changes, and may even threaten food security of masses. Major Contributors of Climate Change are argued to be Developed Countries who have the better technology ecosystem and thus are source of most ESTs. However, developing and underdeveloped countries in tropical region are most likely to face the major brunt of Climate Change. Also, since Developing Countries like India are witnessing increase in developmental activities, emissions of CO₂ are likely to rise as demand for energy is rising due to rise in living standards and high industrial growth. Thus, there is a need for diffusion of ESTs into Developing Countries like India and for further research and development to improve upon existing technologies. Also, this is required to be done in a manner which is affordable to ensure that adopting these technologies is practically feasible for countries whose lack in their economic strength.

1.2. Literature Review

In working paper by *Bronwyn H. Hall & Christian Helmers on The Role of Patent Protection in (Clean/Green) Technology Transfer*¹ the main argument is that Patent Protection alone is insufficient to encourage innovation. It is argued that Patent Protection may encourage diffusion of technology but impacts innovation and R&D over existing technology. It is argued that effective Patent Regime improve Diffusion of technology via increased imports, Investments and licensing mechanisms. Paper² argues that there is no effect on underdeveloped countries while developing countries benefit. We can infer from this inference in paper that there are various other factors that have a combined role to play in diffusion of ESTs. It was inferred in the paper that there can be no uniform solution to encourage transfer of ESTs and factors like geography, industrial progress of the nation, social, economic & political nature of the country in question. Paper³ suggests that governments can use Policy measures like Push and Pull mechanisms to their nation's benefit.

¹ Bronwyn H. Hall & Christian Helmers, *The Role of Patent Protection in (Clean/Green) Technology Transfer* NATIONAL BUREAU OF ECONOMIC RESEARCH.

² *Ibid.*

³ Bronwyn H. Hall & Christian Helmers, *supra* note 1.

Paper⁴ argues that exploitation of Petroleum by Countries like Venezuela, Iran, Indonesia etc. is increased due to subsidies given by the government and thus, there is lack of demand of ESTs in these economies. India and China after year 2000 imposed import tariffs on Solar PVs and Wind, these restricted the transfer of technology to India, whereas China invested in domestic R&D and today has become pioneer in Solar PVs. Import tariffs and subsidies for Biofuels given by U.S. and E.U. has restricted the growth of industrial capacity of developing countries. Germany incentivized Solar PVs which resulted into China flooding German Market leading to political concerns. Overall, 2 groups emerge according to this paper, on one hand is Developing economies like BRICS nations and Mexico who are benefitting from patent regime and licensing, while on other hand are Underdeveloped nations like African nations who are rather disadvantaged by the stringent patent protection.

We can conclude from this paper⁵ that, we should take a more holistic approach and consider all the factors while considering Diffusion of ESTs.

Eric L. Lane in his journal article *Building the Global Green Patent Highway: A Proposal For International Harmonization of Green Technology Fast Track Programs*⁶, as the title suggests, discusses Fast Track processing patent applications of Green Technology patents. Paper argues that accelerated examination has to accompanied by synchronized set of rules because inconsistencies may make process costlier and time consuming. Harmonization into single set of rules is said to be desirable. Streamlining the rules will reduce the workload of the Examiner despite and Examiner will be able to examine a greater number of applications. Some suggestion includes capping number of claims, setting standards for subject matter eligibility and introducing a strict single invention requirement.

Next paper⁷ provides Indian perspective of this issue. It states that India needs to reduce Green House Gas emissions by 33 to 35% by 2030 from 200 levels to meet INDC targets. This paper focuses on carbon sequestration technologies. It is observed from empirical research in this paper that Japan and U.S. are pioneer in the said area. L' Air Liquide is the biggest assignee with 237 patents. Alstom Tech is a new and emerging competitor of L' Air Liquide. Energy demand of India is increasing @4.6 % per year and will thus increase by 100% or will double in next 15 years. We need to reduce fossil fuel dependency. Policy changes like funding for R&D, subsidies, mandating alternate biofuels, tax credits have been suggested. Some radical measures like Compulsory License of all Green Technology has been also suggested which seems to be an impractical solution. It mentions about expedited examination conducted by USPTO in 2009 as a pilot project and argues that such experiments should be tried more. It is argued that IPR presence enhances Technology Transfer via trade, FDI, joint ventures with local partners and licensing mechanisms. Project between EPO, UNEP and ICTSD which served as a public

⁴ Bronwyn H. Hall & Christian Helmers, *supra* note 1.

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ Eric L. Lane, *Building the Global Green Patent Highway: A Proposal for International Harmonization of Green Technology Fast Track Programs*, 27 BERKELEY TECHNOLOGY L.J. 1119 (2012).

⁷ Nishad A. Deshpande & Asha Nagendra, *Climate Mitigation Technologies - Perspective based on Patents*, 21 JOURNAL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS, 337, 337-346 (2016).

information platform that would enable empirical study into Role of IPRs in transfer of CCMTs and ESTs was commended by this article. In the said project Tagging of patent was done if they in any manner helped in Climate Change Mitigation or protection of environment. Since CCMTs and ESTs are rather a multidisciplinary in nature tagging helps in monitoring these patent applications. This paper⁸ states that 71% of all patents are sought in Developed countries which show that market-based demand and economic strength to adapt a technology is the major factor which determines ESTs commercial working. This paper argues for a increased collaboration and research sharing between private companies of different countries as a method for transfer of technology which is supported by the empirical evidence.

Next article is an article from Global Challenges Brief Series of WIPO titled “*The acceleration of climate change and mitigation technologies: Intellectual property trends in the renewable energy landscape*”⁹ which enumerates 4 major types CCMTs with most patenting activity viz. Biofuels, Solar PVs, Solar Thermals and Wind Energy. China and South Korea have most contributions to Solar PVs. 30% of all applications come through Patent Cooperation Treaty route which shows that Technology Transfer is possible via IP Regimes. Paper raises alarm by stating that CO₂ levels have peaked at 400 parts per million and we need to control Green Houses Gas concentration in the atmosphere. Paper’s moot point is that patent based studies can be very good indicators of level of technical development, origin of technologies, who is making the particular technologies, market strength, etc. This information can then help policy makers to make right policy, it can help private entities to better collaborate, countries to make strategic ties by sharing complementary parts of the same EST. This paper enumerates that Policy and Market are also pertinent factors when it comes to EST Transfer either within or between the countries. Biofuel patent application are mainly dominated by Universities especially Chinese Public funded Universities. Wind Energy has no contribution from private sector due to maturity of this segment. In Solar Thermal segment China and Germany are the leader in inventors, however, being capital intensive technology patents are generally licensed and inventors are thus not the operators. Solar PV is dominated by China, Japan and S. Korea with companies like LG, Samsung and Hyundai having substantial R&D investments in this area. Biomass research is decentralized.

This paper¹⁰ concludes that Patent based research can better guide policy makers as to where they should invest for R&D, where should they form partnerships and with whom, how to balance international politics to achieve their EST transfer objectives, where to create Knowledge networks and what are their technical strengths and can they better benefit from existing knowledge within the country. Thus, patent based empirical research is encouraged to be pursued and this paper acts as a source of inspiration for my Dissertation.

Next and last paper for this literature review is again an article from Global Challenges Brief Series of WIPO titled *When policy meets evidence: What's next for the discussion on intellectual*

⁸ Nishad A. Deshpande & Asha Nagendra, *supra* note 8.

⁹ CambridgeIP, *The acceleration of climate change and mitigation technologies: Intellectual property trends in the renewable energy landscape*, WIPO Geneva, www.wipo.int/globalchallenges (2014).

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

*property, technology transfer and the environment?*¹¹ which reiterates many points regarding GHGs, steady increase in EST patent filings, Interaction of Patent Regime with other factors in influencing transfer of ESTs etc. Firstly, this paper defines ESTs as technology which either:

- a) “Protects environment, (thus includes CCMTs)
- b) Is less polluting over prior art,
- c) Use resources in a more sustainable manner,
- d) Recycle more of the wastes, OR
- e) Handle wastes in a more efficient manner”.

Thus, when this paper is compared with other literature already discussed above, we can say that, ESTs are much wider in the ambit than CCMTs. CCMTs generally, only include Carbon Sequestration technologies, low carbon energy and transport technologies. Thus, CCMTs are a subset of ESTs. However, when it comes to patent applications bulk of applications are filed in the field of Solar PVs, Biofuels, Biomass, Solar Thermals and Wind which lie in category of both CCMTs and ESTs.

This paper¹² argues that ESTs are concentrated in the developed countries and that it is done by these countries not only to maintain control over the technology but also to focus only on important markets i.e. Developed Countries themselves.

Overall, two school of thoughts emerge one which argues that effective IP regime tend to foster EST diffusion whereas other say the exact opposite that is effective IP regime hinders EST diffusion into developing countries like India. It is however, seen that various other number of factors also have a significant impact on diffusion. Thus, it would be wrong to ignore these factors.

Hindrances that emerge in paper¹³ mentioned above are:

1. Asymmetric Information.
2. Market Power Externality.
3. Uncertainty about quality of innovation and future input prices.

It is argued that BRIC (Brazil, Russia, China and India) nations have significantly benefitted from better IP implementation in terms of Technology Transfer. At the same time, it is seen that in India Pharmaceuticals have witnessed rapid growth because of lack of patent protection to Pharmaceuticals in nascent years of the industry. It is thus to be noted that impact of Patent regime on Technology Transfer is correlated to the type of innovation in question.

Further, it is argued by Majumdar¹⁴ that duration of patent should not be uniform and that it should be decided on the basis of economic analysis of Marginal Social Cost vs. Marginal Social Benefit analysis. Also, it is suggested by Majumdar¹⁵ to reduce the duration of patent protection

¹¹ M. Perez Pugatch, *When policy meets evidence: What's next for the discussion on intellectual property, technology transfer and the environment?*, WIPO Geneva, www.wipo.int/globalchallenges (2011).

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ Arjya B. Majumdar, *An Economic Analysis of Indian Patent Law*, SSRN Electronic Journal (2013).

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

for pharmaceuticals and software systems. Gifford¹⁶ also reaches the same conclusion with respect to Pharmaceuticals. This shows us that which subject matter the invention belongs to is a very relevant factor in any discussion of the patent.

As argued earlier that Diffusion of ESTs is not a one-dimensional aspect but is dependent upon many other factors. These factors, from the perspective of developing countries, as mentioned in paper¹⁷ discussed above are summarized below:

1. Infrastructure facilities in the country in question.
2. Effectiveness of Governance.
3. Strength of Knowledge Institutions.
4. Financial health of the country in question.
5. Quality of skilled labor.
6. Regulatory Environment.
7. Strategic and Political ties with developed countries.
8. Openness to International Trade.
9. Technical and Organizational capacity to integrate the novel innovation.
10. Extent of spending in R&D to create domestic innovations.
11. Whether International Obligations are abided by properly.
12. And lastly, of course, effective Intellectual Property Rights regime.

The same paper¹⁸ provides following suggestions to developing countries to foster EST diffusion from developed world:

1. Effective IP regime and then licensing of technologies.
2. Joint R&D in collaboration with private or public entities of Developed Countries.
3. Merger and Acquisitions.
4. Strategic Alliances between Developed and Developing nations.
5. Establishing Manufacturing capacity at domestic level.
6. Capacity Building via education, training and improving infrastructure.
7. International cooperation.
8. Financial Support to Researchers.

This paper¹⁹ then provides a very interesting case study of eSolar, a Californian company which was granted patent in India, U.S. and China. Here, Both India and China were able to transfer technology from the U.S. ACME of India invested \$30 Million into eSolar and in return eSolar granted Exclusive License to ACME and in China, Penglai was able to leverage its electric manufacturing capacity. Here it is to be noted that eSolar's decision of granting exclusive license provided ACME and Penglai with certain degree of assurance on returns and was thus able to take the risk of such investment and commitment respectively.

¹⁶ Daniel J. Gifford, *How Do the Social Benefits and Costs of the Patent System Stack Up in Pharmaceuticals?*, 12 J. Intell. Prop. L. 75 (2004).

¹⁷ M. Perez Pugatch, *supra* note 11.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

1.3. Research Objectives

1. To study the effect of patent law protection and its implementation on Diffusion of ESTs (Environmentally Sound Technologies) in India.
2. To find the correlated factors that affects the said Diffusion of ESTs.
3. To find suggestions for Indian Policy makers to better implement Patent regime to promote Diffusion of ESTs into India

1.4. Research Questions

1. What are the factors according to the existing literature, which in conjunction with patent regime affects Diffusion of ESTs?
2. Finding the information about applicants.
 - a. Who are the major applicants for patents of ESTs specifically in subject matter of Solar Thermal, Solar PVs and Wind Energy in India?
 - b. Which countries do these applicants belong to?
3. Analyzing the yearly trends in the said 3 subject matters viz. Solar Thermal, Solar PVs and Wind Energy.
4. Based on findings of questions above,
 - a. Where are the opportunities available for policy makers for increasing Diffusion of ESTs into India, what strategies can be adopted for the same?
 - b. Are inventions originating from certain countries where India can form strategic alliances for diffusion of ESTs?
 - c. Do any complementary technologies exist which can provide private Indian entities a chance to collaborate with their foreign counterparts?
5. What are the suggestions for policy makers for better diffusion of ESTs specifically in subject matter of Solar Thermal, Solar PVs and Wind Energy in India?

1.5. Methodology

The study will first conduct a desk based applied doctrinal research which will include descriptive and analytical research wherein the Role of Patents in Diffusion of ESTs from developed to developing nations more specifically India will be studied. This paper will look at factors that along with Patent Protection affect the diffusion of ESTs. Also, impact of international conventions like TRIPS, UNFCCC, WTO, Paris Treaty on the same would be studied. Solutions more apt for Indian conditions would be discussed.

The study would also incorporate empirical research in the form of findings from data collection done on public patent search system of India Patent Office also known as inPASS available at url: <http://ipindiaservices.gov.in/publicsearch>. However, our research will be restricted to only 3 categories viz. Solar thermal, Solar PVs and Wind Energy. The paper will analyze who are inventors, which country does the technology originates from, statistics in growth of filing of patents on yearly basis. Then an effort will be made to offer one or two concrete suggestions based on empirical evidence to foster diffusion of ESTs into India.

2. INTRODUCTION TO THE TOPIC

2.1. Climate Change and Extreme Weathers

Climate Change is not the past and not the future. It is a reality and it is right now in the present. Climate Change is affecting our weather patterns, instances of drought and floods are on rise simultaneously. While deserts are getting flooded due to incessant rains e.g. Rajasthan in late monsoons, at the same time desertification of northern plains of India is now a serious impending threat. This is eventually bound to cause shortages of food and drinking water which could lead to civil unrest. Mitigation & Adaptation to Climate Change is not about being a liberal or leftist or rightist, which is what political parties of western world, in particular USA, portray it to be. Mitigation & Adaptation to Climate Change is about survival. It's about do and die of human race. Perhaps, our generation would not face extreme effects of Climate Change. But our next generation is going to have to fight tooth and nail for the very survival. It is therefore important to quickly diffuse ESTs so that developing world can become developed without committing the same mistakes as that of developed world. And, perhaps, then only could we achieve 2-degree Celsius limit of the climate change.

2.2. Pollution

As per Greenpeace, “22 of world's 30 most polluted cities are in India”²⁰. And this is not without repercussions. As per a study, “Life expectancy in India has been reduced by 2.6 years due to air pollution”²¹. Asthma patients are rising at a rapid pace, immunity is getting lowered, children in cities like Gurugram are at high risk of lung related permanent diseases later in their life. ESTs could provide a clean way forward and may just reverse this trend of ever-increasing pollution. Reducing pollution is at the very heart of ESTs.

2.3. Population Rise and Rising Electricity Demand

“As per the latest UN report, in 2059, India's population is estimated to peak at 1.65 billion following which it will begin shrinking.”²² Therefore, India needs to strategize for rising Energy demands for transportation, domestic consumption, industrial consumption, other economic activities, social activities and leisure. Energy is consumed not only via electricity or fuel consumption but also in latent activities e.g. every purchase of a consumer good has energy consumption and GHG emissions associated with it in the background.

India has achieved rapid economic growth post LPG reforms of 1990s. But that growth has been mainly derived from tremendous growth in service sector. If India wishes to sustain this high

²⁰ 22 of world's 30 most polluted cities are in India, Greenpeace says, THE GUARDIAN, <https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2019/mar/05/india-home-to-22-of-worlds-30-most-polluted-cities-greenpeace-says>.

²¹ PTI, Life expectancy in India down by 2.6 yrs due to air pollution: Study, ECONOMIC TIMES, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/life-expectancy-in-india-down-by-2-6-yrs-due-to-air-pollution-study/articleshow/69744180.cms>.

²² India must plan for both population growth and decline, TIMES OF INDIA, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/toi-editorials/india-must-plan-for-both-population-growth-and-decline/>.

growth trajectory and reduce its import burden, it needs to enhance its domestic manufacturing which will require substantial amount of electricity. India cannot afford to slow its economic progress for sake of tackling climate change. Further, implosion of the service industry in India has led to creation of sizable middle class in cities which has increased capacity of people to pay for electricity for luxury needs as compared to earlier basic minimums. Simply put people now can afford to pay for temperature control by using air conditioners and heaters as opposed to simple fans earlier. Rural electrification is also on the rise with the present government claiming that it has achieved 100% rural electrification²³ which means that transmission lines have reached all the villages. Next step would be to provide connectivity to the rural house from these transmission lines which would lead to gigantic surge in demand for electricity.

In terms of absolute electricity consumption India ranks third in the world with 1.4 trillion kW-hour/year²⁴ behind U.S. and China with 3.9 and 6.3 trillion kW-hour/year²⁵ respectively. But that does not give us the whole picture. In terms of Per capita electricity consumption India consumes 1122 kWh per capita per year²⁶ while global average is 2674 kWh per capita per year²⁷, U.S.A. uses as much as 12071 kWh²⁸ per capita per year and China uses 4475 kWh per capita per year²⁹. Needless to say, India needs to, or let us say, is bound to see a significant rise in this value. And since India's estimated population now has now crossed 1.35 billion mark³⁰ the demand of electricity is going to be huge. A large chunk of this demand is going to come from the rural areas. Thus, it may be thought of as a good opportunity to provide rural electrification by using non-conventional sources of electricity, in particular let us say, decentralized Solar PVs.

India is facing significant Energy Security challenge which needs to be tackled urgently to ensure social peace, sustainable and equitable development. Electricity demand is growing rapidly while India is way behind in providing universal electricity access. It is important to remember that 80% of India's oil supply is imported which disadvantages India not only in terms of strategic negotiations & self-reliability but also depletes India's Forex reserves while creating an unfavorable trade imbalance. Further, as per India's Climate Action plan under which India has set ambitious target to generate 40% of its energy from non-fossil fuels by 2030. This means India needs to bring Renewables into mainstream and India needs to do it quick. One way could be to create Pan-India market for Renewables.³¹

²³ Suparna Dutt D'Cunha, *Modi Announces '100% Village Electrification', But 31 Million Indian Homes Are Still In The Dark*, FORBES, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/suparnadutt/2018/05/07/modi-announces-100-village-electrification-but-31-million-homes-are-still-in-the-dark/>.

²⁴ Central Statistics Office, *Energy Statistics 2017*, MINISTRY OF STATISTICS AND PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATION, mospi.nic.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Energy_Statistics_2017r.pdf?download=1.

²⁵ *Country Comparison: Electricity – Consumption*, CENTRAL INTELLIGENCE AGENCY, <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/rankorder/2233rank.html>.

²⁶ Central Statistics Office, *supra* note 24.

²⁷ *Supra* note 3.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ REUTERS, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-china-economy-power/chinese-power-consumption-climbed-over-6-percent-in-2017-nea-idUSKBN1FB078>.

³⁰ WORLDOMETERS, <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/india-population/>.

³¹ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

The following pie chart (fig. 1)³² shows distribution of India’s 332 GW installed capacity as on October 2017 (CEA).

And following pie chart (fig. 2)³³ shows distribution within Renewables out of 61 GW (CEA October 2017).

2.4. ESTs and CCMTs

ESTs are “technologies that protect the environment, are less polluting, use all resources in a more sustainable manner, recycle more of their wastes and products, and handle residual wastes in a more acceptable manner than the technologies for which they were substitutes and are compatible with nationally determined socio-economic, cultural and environmental priorities”³⁴.

ESTs have been divided into two basic types viz hard technologies and soft technologies. Examples of ESTs include GM seeds that can tolerate low level of moisture in the soil, technology that improves water use efficiency in the agricultural fields via improved irrigation delivery, etc. On the other hand, examples of soft technologies are inventive financing methods

³² P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ Richard J.T. Klein et al., *Application of environmentally sound technologies for adaptation to climate change*, UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE, <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/docs/2006/tp/tp02.pdf>.

for securing crop insurance for the farmers, new and inventive patterns of alternate selection of the crops to enhance their productivity, etc. Basically, hard technologies rely on physical technologies that have direct applications whereas soft technologies are more focused on knowledge and skills. Both soft and hard technologies work have to be worked in synchronization if desired results are to be achieved.

Another method of classification of the ESTs is categorizing them based on the time period they were developed. Based on this classification there are 4 types of ESTs: traditional, modern, high and future technology.

1. Traditional technologies are those used before the industrial revolution to improve human life e.g. herbal or traditional medicine, dykes to keep out flood waters. Traditional Knowledge Digital Library, TKDL provides information on such technologies that originated in India.
2. Modern technologies belong to era of industrial revolution after usage of coal became prominent with invention of steam engine, usage of crude oil to make human-made materials like plastics, pesticides and fertilizers by using industrial solvents, hybrid varieties of crops, drip irrigation etc.
3. High technologies are recent technologies that may include telecommunications like 4G, 5G, internet, satellite-based navigation, satellites-based mapping like GIS, GMOs, etc.
4. Future technologies are technologies that have are either in the R&D stage and will be developed in the future or those whose ideas have not even been conceived yet. These technologies may be even beyond limits of human imagination. Examples could be cure for rabies, or a method of artificial photosynthesis for production of food at highly efficient rates and low cost, or a method of conversion of solar energy directly into hydrocarbons at 99% efficiency using only non-toxic recyclable minerals and graphene.

ESTs are much wider in the ambit than CCMTs. CCMTs generally, only include Carbon Sequestration technologies, low carbon energy and transport technologies. Thus, CCMTs are a subset of ESTs. However, when it comes to patent applications bulk of applications are filed in the field of Solar PVs, Biofuels, Biomass, Solar Thermals and Wind which lie in category of both CCMTs and ESTs.

2.5. Renewable Energy a Panacea? –A thought with a pinch of salt

This discussion is inspired from a lecture taken up by Prof. Surya Prakash Sethi³⁵. First let us discuss the Load Demand Curve for electricity with respect to time of the day. The graph below (fig. 3)³⁶ shows the generalized Load Demand Curve based on typical domestic and industrial consumption patterns.

³⁵ Surya Prakash Sethi, *Lecture - Let's talk: Solar and Wind*, TERI SAS (23rd January, 2019).

³⁶ Dricus, *Base Load and Peak Load: understanding both concepts*, SINOVOLTAICS, <https://sinovoltaics.com/learning-center/basics/base-load-peak-load/>.

Important things to note in figure above are that:

- Peak Demand occurs twice a day, typically in India around 12 PM and 12 AM. Peak Demand at afternoon is attributed to work timings and later at night due to leisure and factory activities.
- Peak Demand is 1.6 to 1.7 times the Base Demand (Based on area under the curve which signifies Power x time = Energy)
- Overall Installed capacity has to be created roughly 10% above peak loads to provide stability to the grid.

Note that a specific energy source has its own *Inertia* which is due to *ramp up time and ramp down time*. Nuclear has the maximum inertia which is as large as months or even years. Coal and Hydro have medium inertia. Gas turbine has minimum inertia and they can be started or shut down within minutes or even seconds.

- In figure above (fig. 4) we have divided the load into three segments:
 1. Peak Load- This is the load that will be taken up by Gas turbines.
 2. Intermediate load shall be taken up by Coal and Hydro.
 3. Base load will be taken up by Nuclear, Coal and Hydro.

- So, where do we locate the Renewables? Renewables with their intermittency are highly unreliable. Solar will provide energy only during days.

Now let us take the German example which is touted as the success model for renewables in the world. (*Energy Winde Project* – literally means Energy Transformation)

- Germany is Global leader in Solar and Wind energy which are benign for environment.
- In 2017, German Base load was 55 to 60 GWh (80 million people). Peak demand was 85 GWh, convention Sources Installed capacity was 93 GWh which was sufficient to handle all the needs.
- Over and above this Germany had acquired 112 GWh of Solar and Wind installed capacity making total installed capacity to reach at 205 GWh.
- So, on an average half of the energy is wasted by the Germany. Cost of this Energy Winde project is estimated to reach € 1 trillion by 2030.
- India certainly cannot afford such a gigantic waste of taxpayer money and material resources.

India's discussion:

- India is getting Solar power at tariffs of around Rs. 2.45 per kWh by using reverse auctions. Prof. Sethi³⁷ has tactfully implied that there are certain hidden costs in these tariffs.
- As per the opinion of the researcher of the present research paper, these hidden costs could be
 - i. Environmental Costs – rapid project clearances causing deforestation or ecological mayhem.
 - ii. Loss of cultivable farmer's land endangering farmer welfare and food security.
 - iii. Free supply of precious water to these projects. Even Solar PVs need water for cleaning the cells to ensure settled dust does not impede the generation of electricity by PVs.
 - iv. Government concession of state's land to private players.
 - v. Government securities ultimately endangering exchequers financial health if project fails.
 - vi. Similarly, could lead to rise in Public Sector Bank's NPAs if project doesn't fructify.

2.6. Why patents specifically and not any other IPR?

Intellectual Property Rights or IPRs are a creation of human intellect. By way of human intellect and mental labor, humans can create various type of Intellectual Products. They can create:

1. Literary, Dramatic, Artistic or Musical Works which are protected by Copyrights. (Copyright Act, 1957)
2. A certain type of patterns for industrial products which give aesthetically pleasing sensation. These are protected by Designs.

³⁷ Surya Prakash Sethi, *Lecture - Let's talk: Solar and Wind*, TERI SAS (23rd January, 2019).

3. New Plant varieties (Protection of Plant Varieties and Farmers' Rights Act, 2001 enacted as a *sui generis* legislation as per Article 27.3(b) of TRIPS)
4. Trademarks to protect brand names or the word marks or the logos which in the mind of public are associated to certain quality of goods and/or services offered. (Trade Marks Act, 1999)
5. Geographical Indication or GI is like trademarks but they create impression in the minds of public about quality of goods and/or services originating, or manufactured in a geographical region. (Geographical Indications of Goods Act, 1999)
6. Semiconductor Integrated Circuits Layout-Design Act 2000.
7. Inventions are protected by Patents Act, 1970 (as amended).

It is inventions, i.e. products or processes which are converted into machines, devices, medicines, industrial processes, etc. which could be improved upon to become less polluting, to generate electricity from cleaner sources, to create transportation systems which are more efficient like mass transit, to create cities which are more efficient and uses less resources to achieve same output, do direct carbon sequestration, etc. Therefore, laws protecting the inventions are patents and directly affect the ESTs. This is why Patents have been chosen as

2.7. Need of technology transfer, developing world argument

Major Contributors of Climate Change are argued to be Developed Countries who have the better technology ecosystem and thus are source of most ESTs. However, developing and underdeveloped countries in tropical region are most likely to face the major brunt of Climate Change. Also, since Developing Countries like India are witnessing increase in developmental activities, emissions of CO₂ are likely to rise as demand for energy is rising due to rise in living standards and high industrial growth. Thus, there is a need for diffusion of ESTs into Developing Countries like India and for further research and development to improve upon existing technologies. Also, this is required to be done in a manner which is affordable to ensure that adopting these technologies is practically feasible for countries whose lack in their economic strength.

2.7.1. What is Technological Diffusion?

“Technological diffusion is defined widely as the process by which the market for a new technology changes over time and from which production and usage patterns of new products and production processes result.”³⁸ In layman terms, Technological Diffusion is integration of the new technology into relevant products, processes, human skills, industrial infrastructure and market availability in a way that such a technology becomes inherent to the particular field into a new geographical or political jurisdiction. Diffusion is, therefore, the step after the technology has been transferred. While selection of the topic, a conscious choice has been made in selecting the word *Diffusion* over the word *Technology Transfer* since mere Technology transfer of the ESTs is simply not good enough to combat Climate Change. What is now required is *Diffusion* of ESTs into countries like India.

³⁸ Paul Stoneman et al., *The Diffusion of New Technology*, REPEC, https://ideas.repec.org/h/eee/haechp/v2_733.html.

3. IPRs and TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

IPR grants a negative right to the owner of such right wherein owner of such IPR, more particularly patents, has right to “exclude others from making, using, selling, or importing” products or processes if no permission or license is taken from IPR holder³⁹. Whether IPRs are detrimental or beneficial for technology transfer of new technology has been a question to which no satisfactory and conclusive answer has been witnessed so far. Some researchers try to answer this question by dividing the relevant countries into various income groups and thereafter conduct the research. However, different researchers give different results. Major reason for inconsistency in the research work is the very paucity of empirical research on IPRs and Technology Transfer. Another reason for inconsistency in the said results seems to stem from deficiencies in patent databases to begin with. Some of the problems with public databases include traditional style of classification system which does not take into account the growing importance of CCMTs, lack of commercial working data of patents on public databases, etc. These reasons will be discussed in detail later on.

3.1. Relationship

This section is divided into two parts. The first one will look into direct relationship between patents and the other one will focus on indirect factors including market structure.

3.1.1. General Relationship – Patent a hurdle or opportunity?

An opportunity:

It is argued that if any government chooses to enforce stronger protection of the patents, it would enhance the overall patenting activity⁴⁰. Stronger protection inherently implies two dimensions i.e. prosecution dimension and infringement proceeding dimension. Therefore, stronger protection would provide applicant faster grant of patents and better implementation of their rights. This could make filing of patents more lucrative for applicants, therefore, increases patenting activity.

Prosecution dimension means that bonafide inventions could be patentable in very short duration of time. IPO has streamlined a lot of its internal processes by going digital including uploading scanned copies of all relevant documents on inPASS which is a public database and making mandatory for Patent Agents to file application, filling up vacancies in IPO particularly that of Examiners & Controllers, etc. As per Patent law in India expedited examination is available to Start ups and International applications⁴¹ choosing India as ISA, earlier this provision was inculcated to promote startups and to bring in more business for IPO. Expedited examination is planned to be used as a method to improve prosecution by way of certain proposed amendments

³⁹ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 48.

⁴⁰ Patenting activity could be broadly defined as increase in absolute number of patent applications filed in a jurisdiction. More particularly it could be defined as filing of patent applications which have high probability of getting granted. That is to say, patenting activity must ignore frivolous patents e.g. filed by certain private Universities of India merely to get governmental grants and to increase Application numbers to show to potential students their credibility.

⁴¹ Patent Cooperation Treaty applications entering India in National Phase.

which will be discussed in more detail later on. Infringement Dimension means that patentees of granted patents could successfully institute infringement proceedings against the infringers. Infringement suits are primarily instituted in District Courts and High Courts is primarily. It has been observed in recent past that Patentees have been getting favorable judgments and in a timely manner particularly by Indian High Courts. Therefore, India is making strides in strengthening its patent regime.

It could be further argued that since no entity would unnecessarily want to waste its time and money in getting patents for technologies which they don't intend to use. Even where in some cases sole intent of entities for patenting is to *kill-off* the competition, there are some protections available in Indian Patent Act, 1970 which could allay such fears e.g. mandatory requirement of supplying commercial working data⁴² on yearly basis until lifetime of the patent expires. Therefore, based on the arguments provided above, it could be stated that stronger protection of patents would enhance diffusion of technology in India. The same conclusion was also arrived at by Hall and Helmers⁴³.

A Hurdle:

It is often argued that the very reason for success of pharmaceutical industry in India has been because of lack of patentability of products before the 2003 Amendment of Patent Act, 1970. Earlier only processes were patentable. Some even argue that China's manufacturing success also stem from weak implementation of Intellectual Property laws and only strengthening the patent regime after manufacturing ecosystem was well developed. Further, we know that Intellectual Property laws and Anti-Trust laws are in direct conflict with each other and reason is simple Intellectual Property tends to give monopoly rights which is very element anti-trust laws created to tackle. This means that Intellectual Property laws, and in particular patent laws, tend to eliminate competition from the market. It has been generally seen, barring few exceptions, that in markets where monopoly has been cemented, the creation of goods and services become highly inefficient. Therefore, it seems only logical that patenting is anti-innovation and anti-industry.

The balance:

It is important to note that while disclosure of invention in other jurisdictions also discloses the inventions throughout the world including India, however, such disclosure in itself is not sufficient to boost the manufacturing of the EST Technology. Take an example of manufacturing Solar panel with the help of a new invention which uses a complex machine to efficiently manufacture the said panels. In this example, while disclosure might enable an Indian entity to create the said complex machine, they still would lack expertise in using it.

Therefore, on one hand absolutely strict patent regimes would deter innovation by eliminating competition. On the other hand, lenient regimes would not be able to attract sufficient disclosures of technology and even if disclosures take place in other jurisdictions, it would still keep the expertise away.

⁴² More about this is discussed in next chapter.

⁴³ Bronwyn H. Hall and Christian Helmers, *The Role of Patent Protection in (Clean/Green) Technology Transfer*, SANTA CLARA COMPUTER AND HIGH TECHNOLOGY LJ, 26, 487-532.

Patent means to become known or not hidden. Patent is an antonym of word *Latent*. Patent is essentially a contract between Inventor or Inventor's assignee on one hand and Government of a particular jurisdiction on the other hand. Inventor or inventor's assignee discloses the invention fully, particularly and the best method in which it is to be performed. The consideration for the said disclosure is 20 years of monopoly, after which public is free to use the said technology. Ideally, the Inventor or Inventor's assignee would try to commercialize their invention as quickly as possible and create a brand name in the market so that they can reap the benefit of the invention beyond the term of 20 years in form of Trade Mark protection. However, big corporations rely on something more than mere brand name. There is a specific type of proprietary information termed as Trade Secrets considered as a type of Intellectual Property. The said proprietary information usually becomes a key reason in success of any entity and is kept secret from every other competitor. In fact, the most significant barrier in boosting any industry domestically is that of lacking investments and expertise.

Therefore, based on above reasoning, it could be argued that granting patents to genuine inventions should be the way forward.

3.1.2. Other Integrated factors

Patenting of ESTs alone would not be able to boost their diffusion. Multiple factors in tandem with patenting regime influence the diffusion of ESTs.

Firstly, one of the most important factors is the infrastructure. Infrastructure is the key driver of any manufacturing activity of any economy. Infrastructure provides opportunity for transport of raw materials to the factory & delivery of manufactured product thereafter. Infrastructure is not limited to transportation only and also includes water supply, sewage treatment, power, telecom-internet services, financial systems etc. which are not only essentials but their quality also determines whether a manufacturing activity would be economically viable or not.

Secondly, Governance is also another important factor. Governance would determine whether government by way of its policies and schemes is able to push the ESTs in right direction or not. Governance also includes providing hospitals, policing, security forces for industries, education to create skilled labor etc. In India, PPP mode of development has provided success in sectors which were struggling to pick by traditional methods. PPP could also provide way forward for India to boost diffusion of ESTs and CCMTs into India.

Thirdly, Knowledge Institutions play very important role in learning the known methods and technologies, disseminating them in industries, and promoting further innovation. Fourthly, overall economic and financial performance of any economy would determine whether they can shift the focus on ESTs rather than cheaper dirty technologies which rely on hydrocarbons and coal. Fifthly, human resources play one of the most critical roles in quick adoption of new technology, therefore, skilling of labor is crucial. It is in this context that Government of India has been pushing for 'Skill India' mission.

Sixthly, overall regulatory environment in a country plays a very important role in diffusion of ESTs. Usually, we think that only policies related to green technologies would affect the diffusion. But that is not the complete truth. The policies regarding clearances given and support

provided by the government for ESTs are undoubtedly crucial for their diffusion. But decline of governmental support for *dirty technologies* is equally important. Imposing Carbon tax is a very good way forward of promoting adoption of ESTs. Wherein in an embodiment of Carbon tax, carbon tax would impose taxation on usage of coal and hydrocarbon-based sources of energy, and a tax so collected would then be utilized in R&D of ESTs and/or subsidizing their adoption.

Seventhly, foreign relations and strategic ties with technological superpowers determine the bargaining position a developing country like India is going to possess for better diffusion of ESTs. Foreign Relations have been extreme importance in India, to an extent that Indian state can even curtail Fundamental Rights of Indian Citizens to maintain “friendly relations with foreign States”⁴⁴ Since India lacks in R&D and has to rely on technological superpowers for the same, forming geostrategic ties in conformity with internal political scenario is of paramount importance. Indian Patent Office’s draft policy on Japan Patent Prosecution Highway is significant step forward in that direction. Choosing Japan as a first nation for such Patent Prosecution mechanism is not an arbitrary decision of Government of India, rather, it is a well thought decision. More will be discussed about the said Prosecution mechanism in detail later on.

Eighthly, in a Globalized World anything and everything is now interconnected by strings of international trade. India can easily leverage diffusion of ESTs from a country if there is a good balanced trade going on with that country. In ongoing trade war of China-U.S.A. trade dispute wherein South China Sea dispute led to retaliatory custom duties imposed by U.S.A. administration which was, further, quickly followed by Huawei’s demands of amount exceeding \$1 billion⁴⁵ in licensing fees from the telecom operators of U.S.A. And while arguments from both sides, i.e. patent a hurdle or opportunity, have been presented earlier in this chapter; some experts argue that patents are essentially arms and ammunitions of modern warfare known as economics which is seen clearly in latest licensing fee demand of Huawei. It is to be observed that while U.S. and China are two economic giants who are very closely interconnected by trade and investments, latest trade dispute shows that trade is also interconnected with geopolitics. Further, trade tensions between India and U.S.A. has been on the rise because of removal of India from list of Generalized System of Preferences by the U.S. which prompted India into imposing retaliatory custom duties on goods originating from U.S.A. In current scenario it won’t be possible by India to ask for U.S. companies to transfer the EST into India. Therefore, a country needs to balance its trade in line with its EST diffusion aspirations to achieve any success.

Ninthly, since ESTs are new in nature for the technical institutions of India, their technical and organizational ability would determine how quickly they are able to understand and replicate these technologies.

Tenthly, public and private investment in R&D to create indigenous technology is only economically sustainable way forward to fully utilize the potential of ESTs. Further, without any such R&D it is tough to create ESTs which are best suitable for conditions which are specific to India. India’s supply chain is unorganized as opposed to organized in developed world and India’s weather is tropical as opposed to temperate weather of developed world. This necessitates

⁴⁴ INDIA CONST. art. 19 (2).

⁴⁵ Paul Mozur and Edmund Lee, *Huawei Is Said to Demand Patent Fees From Verizon*, NEW YORK TIMES, <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/06/12/technology/huawei-verizon-patent-license-fees.html>.

at least having enough R&D capacity to adapt ESTs of developed world quickly into Indian conditions.

3.2. International Legal Framework

International law provides a framework and boundaries to developing countries like India which influences domestic laws, governmental policies and, ultimately, diffusion of technology itself. Therefore, it is important to understand the International Legal Framework, in order to either minimize the shortcomings of the said framework or to utilize the full potential of advantages located therein. Since the present research is focusing on diffusion of technology across the jurisdiction, it is important to understand based on which treaties, priority is provided to foreign patent applications in order to avoid anticipation⁴⁶.

3.2.1. Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1883

“The Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, signed in Paris, France, on 20 March 1883, was one of the first intellectual property treaties. The substantive provisions of the Convention fall into three main categories: national treatment, priority right and common rules.” National Treatment means a patent application originating outside the jurisdiction shall be treated on par with those originating in the said jurisdiction itself. Priority Right shall be derived from the foreign patent document if the corresponding application is filed within 12 months from date of priority in the relevant jurisdiction. Paris treaty is active and has 177 member countries. Paris treaty route is preferred over PCT route if Applicant is generally interested in a limited number of jurisdictions; let us say less than 10 jurisdictions.

3.2.2. Patent Cooperation Treaty, 1970

Patent Cooperation Treaty, is an international treaty just like the Paris treaty to provide Patent applications right to Priority from the parent domestic application from one jurisdiction to designated jurisdiction which are members to the treaty. An application under PCT route is referred to as a PCT application or an International application. Presently 152 countries are party to this treaty.

The process of making an application through PCT route, in an embodiment, comprises the steps of;

- filing of domestic application which shall become the priority document for all the further applications in the patent family;
- filing of PCT or International application with the WIPO;

⁴⁶ Anticipation, in an embodiment, could be described as knowledge of public of the invention by publication, conference, exhibition or working of the invention. Anticipation leads to destruction of novelty. It is, therefore, crucial for foreign applicants to establish priority based on the domestic patent application using PCT or Paris treaty in order to avoid anticipation and maintain novelty.

selecting an ISA to prepare an ISR and Written Opinion. Indian Applicants can choose ISA from one of the following: Austrian Patent Office, Australian Patent Office, European Patent Office, Indian Patent Office, China Intellectual property Office, United States Trademark & Patent Office or Swedish Patent Office;
going for an optional preliminary examination by an IPEA whose decision is binding neither on the Applicant nor on the designated Patent Office; and
filing a NP application in one or more of the designated jurisdictions selected in the corresponding PCT application within 30 months or 31 months or 32 months from priority date depending upon the jurisdiction, more particularly within 31 months if NP application is entering into India.

This process is then followed by domestic jurisdiction and laws. It should be made clear that – “A PCT application does not itself result in the grant of a patent, since there is no such thing as an ‘international patent’, and the grant of patent is a prerogative of each national or regional authority.”⁴⁷

There are certain advantages of using PCT route over Paris route. One of them is that PCT route provides additional time to the Applicant to decide which in designated jurisdictions it shall proceed with the national phase application based on market research, saving on attorney and office fees of filing unnecessary applications. Another advantage of PCT route is that ISR and Written Opinion generated by the ISA provides opportunity to applicant to amend the application accordingly which increases the chances of Patent getting granted. Paris route is beneficial if Applicant wishes to enter in only handful of Jurisdictions and is confident about patentability of the application.

3.2.3. WTO Framework

“The WTO is an intergovernmental organization that is concerned with the regulation of international trade between nations. The WTO officially commenced on 1 January 1995 under the Marrakesh Agreement, signed by 123 nations on 15 April 1994, replacing the GATT, which commenced in 1948. It is the largest international economic organization in the world.”⁴⁸ “The WTO deals with regulation of trade in goods, services and intellectual property between participating countries by providing a framework for negotiating trade agreements and a dispute resolution process aimed at enforcing participants' adherence to WTO agreements, which are signed by representatives of member governments and ratified by their parliaments.”⁴⁹

The most basic principle which WTO enforces is National Treatment, wherein member states cannot distinguish between domestic and foreign goods. Article III.4 of GATT states that “The products of the territory of any contracting party imported into the territory of any other contracting party shall be accorded treatment no less favorable than that accorded to like

⁴⁷ *Oxonica Energy v. Neuftec Limited*, BRITISH AND IRISH LEGAL INFORMATION INSTITUTE, <http://www.bailii.org/ew/cases/EWHC/Patents/2008/2127.html>

⁴⁸ *The GATT years: from Havana to Marrakesh*, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION, https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/fact4_e.htm.

⁴⁹ *Understanding the WTO*, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION, www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/understanding_e.pdf.

products of national origin in respect of all laws, regulations and requirements affecting their internal sale, offering for sale, purchase, transportation, distribution or use.”⁵⁰ The nations have to treat the foreign goods as if they originated in their own nation. Critically, it may be argued that the National Treatment principle has diminished the need to transfer technology. The imports have become competitive since developed members of WTO persuade other members to lower the direct (lowering of custom duties) and indirect barriers. This is argued to have hurt least developed and developing countries as their domestic industry succumbs to cheaper and superior quality goods originating from developed countries due to their well-developed industry structure and technological prowess.

The above argument can be substantiated by India-U.S. Solar Panel dispute case of WTO. Under Jwaharlal Nehru National Solar mission, domestic content requirement was kept as high as 50%. This move was aimed at boosting the domestic manufacturing Solar PV modules and cells. Art III.8 a of GATT states that – “NT Provisions shall not apply to laws, regulations or requirements governing the procurement by governmental agencies of products purchased for governmental purposes and not with a view to commercial resale or with a view to use in the production of goods for commercial sale.” The content requirement was for solar cells and/or modules; however, the purpose was not of commercial resale of the said modules and/or cells but was generation of electricity and its sale. Therefore, the exception III.8 a of GATT didn’t apply. Further, Article XX of GATT states that “Subject to the requirement that such measures are not applied in a manner which would constitute a means of arbitrary or unjustifiable discrimination between countries where the same conditions prevail, or a disguised restriction on international trade, nothing in this Agreement shall be construed to prevent the adoption or enforcement by any contracting party of measures: (d) necessary to secure compliance with laws or regulations which are not inconsistent with the provisions of this Agreement, (j) essential to the acquisition or distribution of products in general or local short supply;” India was not able to successfully prove that the any of the domestic instruments related to environmentally sound sustainable development was at peril if such National Treatment was granted to Solar Modules and/or cells. Nor could India prove that XX(d) exception with relevant facts as per WTO ruling. WTO ruling had adverse impact to manufacturing ability and diffusion of green technology into India. Therefore, WTO plays an intricate role in technology transfer.⁵¹

WTO Ministers had realized this in Doha Declaration itself and, therefore, created a *Working Group* for “Studying whether the WTO should have more specific measures” to facilitate Technology Transfer. Doha Mandate, para 37 states that Trade and transfer of technology “37. We agree to an examination, in a Working Group under the auspices of the General Council, of the relationship between trade and transfer of technology, and of any possible recommendations on steps that might be taken within the mandate of the WTO to increase flows of technology to developing countries.”⁵²

Developing countries like India have urged to make provisions of trade and technology transfer more functional rather than just ideas. Developing countries have argued that developed countries keep tariffs’ higher on processed goods and maintain lower rate for raw materials (the

⁵⁰ The General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, art. III.4.

⁵¹ Nidhi Srivastava, *Energy Law Lecture – Renewable Energy*, TERI SAS.

⁵² DOHA WTO MINISTERIAL 2001, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION, https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/minist_e/min01_e/mindecl_e.htm#technology.

concept of tariff peaks and tariff escalation), which is adverse to technology transfer as manufacturing is discouraged in developing countries due to such policy. Developing countries have, above all, specifically asked “to look at WTO provisions which have the effect of hindering transfer of technology to developing countries (including intellectual property)”⁵³ On the other hand, “Developed countries have emphasized the danger in coercing the private sector into giving away its technology. Developed countries believe that this would reduce the appeal for foreign direct investment.”

Therefore, trade directly affects and possibly hinders Transfer of technology which is a cause of concern for developing countries. At the same time, multinationals belonging to developed countries are worried that they won’t be able to reap the benefits due to them because of time and money spent by them on R&D. This research tries to find solutions that will allay concerns of both sides.

3.2.4. Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights

“TRIPS is an international legal agreement between all the member nations of the WTO. It sets down minimum standards for the regulation by national governments of many forms of IP as applied to nationals of other WTO member nations and is, therefore, administered by the WTO.”⁵⁴

TRIPS builds upon principles of Paris Treaty, 1883. It advances the idea of national treatment for inventions originating from other jurisdictions. Article 27.1 of TRIPS mandates that both product and process shall be patentable. Article 27.1 further sets 3 criteria based on which grant of refusal of patent application shall be determined. These are Novelty / Newness, Inventive Step / Non-obviousness and Industrial Application. Section 2 (1) (j) of the Indian Patent Act, 1970 (as amended) includes all the above-mentioned features of Article 27.1 of TRIPS.

TRIPS also envisages that all field of technology shall be treated on par with each other and this basically rules out adding Green technology into the Section 3 of Indian Patent Act which describe which types of invention are non-patentable. Article 27.2 provides exclusion of invention which are in conflict with public order or morality and further provides that an invention so excluded on public order or morality ground cannot be commercially worked or sold in that jurisdiction. Thus, a developing country may choose to exclude patentability of technologies that may harm the environment on a condition that they may not work the invention commercially. Without going into detail, it is further worth noting that, Article 27.3(a) of TRIPS provides exclusions related to method of treatment whose language is similar to that of Section 3 (i) of Indian Patent Act. And Article 27.3 (b) is similar to that of Section 3(j) of Indian Patent Act and Protection of Plant Variety and farmer Rights Act,2001 read together.⁵⁵

⁵³ *TRADE AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER Studying whether the WTO should have more specific measures*, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION, https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/minist_e/min03_e/brief_e/brief18_e.htm.

⁵⁴ Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights art. 1(3).

⁵⁵ *The WTO Trips Agreement – A Practical Overview for Climate Change Policymakers*, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION, https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/trips_e/ta_docs_e/8_3_overviewclimatechange_e.pdf.

Therefore, it is argued that Indian Patent law is completely aligned to the TRIPS agreement. And the idea of excluding ESTs from Patentability is simply not possible.

3.2.5. Climate Change Negotiations - UNFCCC Framework

The idea to create an international environmental treaty, in particular to tackle climate change, originated in the Rio Earth summit of 1992. Thereafter, when sufficient member had ratified it in 1994, The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change or UNFCCC came into existence with primary objective to "stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system".⁵⁶

“Under UNFCCC technology transfer framework was created in 2001 and father Expert Group on Technology Transfer to analyze technology development and transfer issues”.⁵⁷ Later in 2010, the Technology Executive Committee was tasked with “identifying policies that can accelerate the development and transfer of low-emission and climate resilient technologies.”⁵⁸ In 2007, 4 key areas were identified where focus is needed to improve diffusion of CCMTs. These are: “Innovative financing; International cooperation; Endogenous development of technologies; and Collaborative research and development.”⁵⁹

Article 4.5 of UNFCCC states that “the developed country Parties and other developed Parties included in Annex II shall take all practicable steps to promote, facilitate and finance, as appropriate, the transfer of, or access to, environmentally sound technologies and know-how to other Parties, particularly developing country Parties, to enable them to implement the provisions of the Convention. In this process, the developed country Parties shall support the development and enhancement of endogenous capacities and technologies of developing country Parties. Other Parties and organizations in a position to do so may also assist in facilitating the transfer of such technologies.”⁶⁰

While UNFCCC is more of a persuasive body than an enforcing one, it is a body which at least bring all parties to deliberate on the issue of climate change which may decide on future of existence of human race. Critics have argued that UNFCCC lack teeth and persuasion is not good enough anywhere as we are way past the mark where we can afford to make any further mistakes as 2-degree Celsius target looks now more and more difficult. Further, with U.S. President deciding to opt out of Paris Deal commitments is a major blow to tackling climate change. Paris deal relied on the principles of “Common but differentiated responsibility” and encouraged countries to decide their own commitments and thereafter stick by them. However, even after U.S. withdrawal from the treaty India, China and other nations remain resolute in upholding their end of the commitments which is an encouraging sign.

⁵⁶ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, art. 2.

⁵⁷ *Technology Transfer Framework*, UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE, <https://unfccc.int/ttclear/tec/tech-transfer-framework.html>.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

⁶⁰ Richard J.T. Klein et al., *Application of environmentally sound technologies for adaptation to climate change*, UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE, <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/docs/2006/tp/tp02.pdf>.

3.2.6. WIPO Green

“WIPO GREEN is an interactive marketplace that promotes innovation and diffusion of green technologies. It does this by connecting technology and service providers with those seeking innovative solutions.”⁶¹ WIPO GREEN was established by WIPO in 2013. WIPO Green relies on internet to make this marketplace viable. It creates Newsletters which are delivered to potential IPR holder or entities looking to get a license or access for these technologies. It provides a digital platform where an interested party can upload their technology in an effort to work it commercially. Users can also upload their “Needs” following which IPR holder can contact the interested user. Technological experts are also available on this platform who catalyze the *matchmaking* process.

The figure above (fig. 5)⁶² highlights the partnership arenas and structure of the WIPO GREEN. This shows that WIPO GREEN is an inclusive organization and has a vision to integrate all the relevant stakeholders into one platform in multidisciplinary & holistic manner to achieve its goals. According to WIPO GREEN’s 2018 report⁶³, it created more than 645 connections, now has 86 partners and 5 deals were made on this platform. While these numbers may seem small, it is a benign beginning.

WIPO GREEN in its Strategic plan of 2019-2023⁶⁴ highlighted its three goals and one strategic objective:

⁶¹ *WIPO GREEN – The Marketplace for Sustainable Technology*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, <https://www3.wipo.int/wipogreen/en/>.

⁶² *WIPO GREEN strategic plan, 2019–2023*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_greenstrp11923.pdf.

⁶³ *WIPO GREEN Year in Review 2018*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_greenreport_2018.pdf.

⁶⁴ *Supra* note 61.

Goal 1: “Link green technology providers and those seeking solutions in a targeted manner, catalyzing and maximizing the potential for green technology transfer and diffusion.”⁶⁵

Goal 2: “Accelerate access to green technology innovation opportunities for countries at all levels of development.”⁶⁶

Goal 3: “Support member states to leverage IP and innovation in global efforts to address major policy issues related to climate change, food security, and the environment.”⁶⁷

“Strategic Objective 1: Increase the capacity of the WIPO GREEN database to accurately, effectively, and efficiently match technology needs with green technology offerings.”⁶⁸

These goals and strategic objectives are an ideal way forward to achieve Diffusion of ESTs and tackling Climate Change. Technologies that are part of WIPO GREEN are those as defined by UNFCCC as ESTs. WIPO GREEN envisages license mechanisms, collaboration between various entities like research institutions, multinationals, green startups etc., creation of joint ventures to execute a project and direct sale of technology as its methodology to achieve its Goals.

3.2.7. Sustainable Development Goals

“The SDGs are a collection of 17 global goals set by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015 for the year 2030. The SDGs are part of Resolution 70/1 of the United Nations General Assembly, the 2030 Agenda.”⁶⁹ Amongst these 17 goals some goals are directly related to Diffusion of ESTs while others are indirectly related. On a more careful look, it can be realized that by Diffusion of ESTs all the SDGs are advanced some to smaller extent while others to larger extent. The Goals that have direct relation to the present subject matter of research are discussed below.

SDG 17: Partnership for the Goals – directly talks about Transfer of technology, in particular, ESTs to achieve Sustainable Development. Target 17.7 states that “Promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries on favorable terms, including on concessional and preferential terms, as mutually agreed”⁷⁰ Target 17.7 directly talks about ESTs. Firstly, Development of ESTs domestically is crucial for developing countries. As it has been argued earlier in the chapter, any technology so transferred is going to have to be further refined to suit to weather and industrial structure of the developing countries like India. However, R&D cannot be done from the scratch and therefore, transfer and diffusion of ESTs from developed world is necessary. Developing countries cannot afford huge licensing fees and, therefore, preferential terms are required. Earlier it was argued that expertise and proprietary information are crucial for success of any industry therefore,

⁶⁵ *WIPO GREEN strategic plan, 2019–2023*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_greenstrp1923.pdf.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ *Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*, UNITED NATIONS, <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>.

⁷⁰ *Goal 17: Revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development*, UNITED NATIONS, <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/globalpartnerships/>.

collaboration on mutual agreed terms is crucial for true realization of ESTs in the developing countries.

SDG 7 – Affordable and Clean Energy: Envisages “achieving universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services; increasing substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix; improving energy efficiency; and enhancing international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology.”⁷¹ Therefore, in order for developing countries like India to realize SDG 7 it is crucial for diffusion of clean energy technology via international cooperation. SDG 13 – Climate Change Action: would also be directly benefitted by quicker adoption of ESTs by the developing countries.

The table below (Table 1) enumerates how SDGs are advanced by ESTs. It is to be noted that technologies that have been considered as ESTs by the UNFCCC have been divided in 7 following broad categories by the IPC Committee of Experts: Alternative Energy Production; Transportation; Energy Conservation; Waste management; Agriculture/Forestry; Administrative, regulatory and design aspects; and Nuclear Power generation.

SDG Advanced	How?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDG 1 – No Poverty • SDG 3 – Good Health and Well Being. • SDG 7 – Affordable and Clean Energy • SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth • SDG 13 – Climate Action 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced pollution by use of Alternative Energy and Waste Management improves sanitation which provides good health, therefore, reduces economic burden of medicines. • Mass transportation provides more economic opportunities to the poor. • Creation of new green jobs and Reduced GHG emissions by using Alternative Energy ESTs. • Energy Conservation ESTs reduce Hydrocarbons required for energy production.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDG 2 – Zero Hunger • SDG 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation • SDG 14 – Life Below Water • SDG 15 – Life on Land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture and Forestry related ESTs reduces dependency on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, conserve water. Thereby, improves livelihood as well. And protects land based ecosystems. Reduces Pesticides runoff and therefore protects freshwater ecosystems as well. • Waste management ESTs improve sanitation, land based ecosystems, freshwater ecosystems and marine ecosystems as well.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure • SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diffusion of ESTs triggers manufacturing and promotes industry and opens up new opportunities for R&D institutions. • Administrative, regulatory and design aspects category of ESTs include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ static design ESTs which improves upon infrastructure and creates Sustainable Cities

⁷¹ *Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy*, UNITED NATIONS, <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/energy/>.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Carbon/Emission trading like pollution credits based ESTs make communities sustainable and make consumption more responsible.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDG 4: Quality Education • SDG 5: Gender Equality • SDG 10: Reduced Inequality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better environment and industrial growth triggered by clean technologies would create more opportunities for all and specially for poor. This would provide them more economic means to afford the education. Further, industrial growth would provide government more funds to boost the social spending on education, Gender Equality and reduce inequalities.

3.3. Summary of Chapter 3

IPRs, specifically patents, are usually anti-competitive which is not good for industry. But they also provide for an opportunity for licensing-based or investment-based diffusion of technology by transfer of skill, expertise and trade secrets. Patenting regime works with other integrated factors to affect the diffusion of ESTs. Most of these factors can be change into favorable factors by India but the change is going to be extremely slow as most of these factors are that of relating to physical, financial, industrial and political infrastructure. Paris Treaty and PCT are crucial for retaining the priority when filing applications in multiple jurisdictions. Trade, WTO, and TRIPS play an intricate role as well. TRIPS under WTO framework enforces national treatment for Patents from other jurisdictions. WTO aims to lower direct and indirect barriers of trade. UNFCCC envisions diffusion of ESTs to achieve Climate Change objective. Diffusion of ESTs is going to help in making significant advances in the various SDGs.

The suggestion based on this chapter emanates from the idea of WIPO Green. While achievement of WIPO Green has been extremely limited, but it is a big step in right direction. After an extensive research on WIPO Green, the present research was unable to find a single fault in the WIPO Green Concept. WIPO Green is a sort of online marketplace wherein EST seekers post their needs, patentee upload the basic info on their technology which they are willing to collaborate or license the technology. The WIPO Green focusses on Green startups. India should take active participation in the WIPO Green. Further India could collaborate with the partners of WIPO Green to start an Indian chapter of the parent WIPO Green for better diffusion of ESTs into India

4. INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

This chapter aims to analyze Indian landscape, its suitability to technology transfer and diffusion. This chapter has been divided into two parts covering legal and policy of IPRs in India and diffusion of ESTs.

4.1. Policy Dimension

Policy is usually the first step which sets the path of a nation in a particular field of application. Policy is then followed by legislation and its implementation. Following which there are several practical issues that are observed and this provides feedback to the first step of Policy. The Policy is then tweaked and process then repeats.

India as such has no policy on Diffusion of ESTs. While there has been some noise regarding India opting to go for Compulsory Licensing route or excluding Green Technology from patentability⁷², it has been argued in the third chapter of the present research that such policy would be in violation of TRIPS agreement and, therefore, better policy measures are needed. The policy measures with respect to Climate Change are discussed herein.

4.1.1. Climate Change Policy

While there is no specific law related to Climate Change law in India, NAPCC, 2008 is an Action Plan made by Government of India to make efforts towards Climate Change Mitigation and Adaption, and to achieve India's commitments under UNFCCC framework. The plan "identifies measures that promote our development objectives while also yielding co-benefits for tackling climate change effectively."⁷³ And further, it states that per capita GHG emissions "will at no point exceed that of developed countries even as we pursue our development objectives."⁷⁴

Under NAPCC Eight Missions have been envisaged to accomplish Climate Change goals of India. These are:

1. Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission: Aims at making power generation using solar PVs and/or thermals more competitive to conventional sources of energy that rely mainly on hydrocarbons and coal. It also includes building institutional capacity for R&D purposes and international collaboration. Mission also envisages building domestic capacity to make Solar power related equipment.
2. National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency: This mission is built over existing statute of the Energy Conservation Act, 2001 which mandated energy audits and Power Savings labelling system on appliances. It introduces concept of energy savings certificates wherein big companies and industries that are big energy guzzlers can trade with each other in order

⁷² Swarup Kumar and Jitesh Kumar, *Easing the path for green tech in India*, REMFRY AND SAGAR, <https://www.remfry.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/easing-the-path-for-green-tech-in-india.pdf>.

⁷³ NAPCC, MINISTRY OF ENVIRONMENT, FOREST AND CLIMATE CHANGE, <http://envfor.nic.in/ccd-napcc/>.

⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

to increase net energy efficiency. Further, direct and indirect incentives are provided to promote the use of energy efficient appliances. Direct incentives include subsidies e.g. on 5 star rated Air Conditioners subsidy is available if consumer wishes to exchange the old appliance, LEDs have been widely subsidized by many state governments and the central government. Indirect incentives include but is not limited to tax-based deductions. Awareness programmes to reduce consumption are also included in this mission.

3. National Mission on Sustainable Habitat: This mission focuses on urban planning as a way to reduce emissions by creating urban spaces that automatically lowers demand for energy. Public transport system like rapid railway systems; last mile connectivity using multi modal integrated mass transit wherein roadways, railways, waterways and airways are optimized to supplement each other; promotion of fuel economy efficient and less polluting vehicles like CNG based and electric vehicles, etc. are envisaged as way to reduce emissions originating from private vehicles. Further, incinerators are touted as a solution to waste management problem while providing extra energy to the grid.
4. National Water Mission: This mission proposes to address serious issue of water scarcity using water pricing, water metering, etc.
5. National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem: The goal of this mission aims to protect physical and biological characteristics of Himalayas. Himalayas are rich in Biodiversity and Forest Cover, however, with rampant exploitation and climate change Himalayas are now threatened. Himalayas are source of most of the perennial rivers and entire Indo-Gangetic plain rely on it for agricultural and other human needs, however with rising global temperatures have resulted into recession of glaciers to higher altitudes where glaciers volumes are much lower threatening the very water security of India. Therefore, this Mission is very crucial for mitigation and adaption to adverse consequences of climate change.
6. National Mission for a “Green India”: This mission aims at Afforestation and Reforestation of degraded forest lands to increase forest cover.
7. National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture: Food security is the biggest challenge posed by climate change. This mission focuses on sustainable agricultural practices. This mission envisages R&D for developing drought-resilient crops. It further envisages creation of new crop insurance mechanisms.
8. National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change: The plan envisages a Climate Science Research Fund for improved weather forecasts by developing better simulation and forecasting models enabling better preparedness in collaboration with strategic partner countries of India.

If we consider the table provided at the end of the third chapter, we will observe that all the Missions under NAPCC mentioned above are going to be significantly advanced by the diffusion of ESTs in India. Therefore, there is a need to create a policy specifically for ESTs and its ardent implementation thereon.

4.1.2. Renewable Energy Policy

Indian Government’s Policy has a significant impact on renewables and this can be seen from graphical representation below (fig. 6)⁷⁵.

While the effect is never immediate, however, it is substantial and is felt over a long gestation period. Therefore, careful planning is needed for better policy creation and implementation.

India has made a commitment in Paris Climate deal whereby it shall reduce emissions and having at least 40 % electric power installed capacity from clean energy sources by the year 2030. Planned distribution of this electric power by renewables (Mission 175 GW by 2022) is as follows (fig. 7)⁷⁶:

While wind energy is required to be doubled, solar power needs to be increased seven-fold to utilize India’s geographical nature of being a tropical country. Main focus is on only these two sources of energy because of their large potential. Solar capacity in India has increased from

⁷⁵ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

meager 3MW in 2008-09 to 12,288MW in 2016-17, and one of the factors for such exponential growth could be because of corresponding exponential reduction in the solar tariff which stood at Rs. 17.91 per kWh in 2010-11 to Rs. 2.44 per kWh in 2017-18. This sharp reduction in tariff can be attributed to state's intervention and regulatory measures. These measures include⁷⁷:

1. Mitigation of the risk in the process at the Bidding Stage.
 - a. Over and above off-take purchase agreement, the off-takers now provide guarantees by off-takers e.g. a two-month payment guarantee issued by PSUs like GAIL or NTPC or SECI in event of default in payment by DISCOMs.
 - b. Online reverse bidding⁷⁸ which not only encourages competition but also provide lower rates due to increased transparency.
 - c. Increase the scale of the projects making it easier to achieve economies of scale and, therefore, resulting in lowering the bids. Other benefits may include increased pace of clearances by the government, better pooling of funds and efficient utilization of the grid.
2. Reduction in Engineering Procurement and Construction costs due to cheaper technology and more competition.
3. Interest shown by the big multinationals resulting into widening of sources of investments and concessional financing wherein foreign governments support their domestic manufacturers to bid in India by providing counter guarantees.⁷⁹

Policy Timeline:

- 1982 – Department of non-Conventional Energy Sources formed
- 1992 – became a Ministry – MNRE (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy)
- 2003 – Electricity Act
- National Electricity Policy, 2005
- NAPCC 2008-09.
- National Tariff Policy, 2016

National Electricity Policy, 2005 focuses on Renewable energy. It aims at enhancing renewable energy generation by lowering the cost incurred in the projects. It envisages procurement of the renewable energy by DISCOMs through competitive bidding.⁸⁰ Further, National Tariff Policy, 2016 aims at enhancing electricity generation from renewable sources⁸¹ by:

- A. Renewable Purchase Obligations, wherein State Electricity Regulatory Commissions will set RPO requirements gradually increasing it to 8% of Solar by 2022.
- B. Renewable Generation Obligations was proposed wherein generator may be required to generate certain percentage of Electricity from renewable sources.
- C. Renewable Energy Certificates wherein certificates are given as a tradable option so that entities of deficient states can trade with surplus state to meet their RPO targets. National Tariff Policy, 2016 envisages REC Mechanism to develop a separate solar specific REC

⁷⁷ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

⁷⁸ "A reverse bidding has one buyer and many potential sellers. In an ordinary auction/forward auction, buyers compete to obtain goods/services by offering increasingly higher prices. In contrast, in a reverse auction, the sellers compete to obtain business from the buyer and prices will typically decrease as the sellers underbid each other."

⁷⁹ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

⁸⁰ Nidhi Srivastava, *Energy Law Lecture – Renewable Energy*, TERI SAS.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*

mechanism. Following figure explains more about REC mechanism⁸² RECs are tradable at Indian Energy Exchange (IEX) & Power Exchange India Limited (PXIL).

Institutional Structure for Regulatory Framework of Renewables in India (fig. 8)⁸³:

Schemes of Government of India for promotion of Renewables:

- A. *Surya Mitra Scheme* focusses on skill development of labor and in particularly of that of youth. The skills imparted would relate to installation of Solar PVs or Solar thermals and their maintenance.
- B. *Solar Photovoltaic Installation (SPIN)* is related to promotion of grid connected rooftop systems in homes via online monitoring. A new website has been created for this purpose namely solarrooftop.gov.in wherein a calculator based on financial capacity / area available / type of building/ EMI duration gives users a fair estimate of financial viability of the panel. Under JNNSM, the Grid connected Rooftop generation target is 40 GW by 2022.
- C. *Kisan Urja Suraksha evam Utthaan Mahabhiyan (KUSUM) Scheme* (28,250 MW) wherein farmers will use their barren land for solar energy projects and use/sell the generated electricity. The cost division shall be as follows: Government of India. – 60%(subsidy); Banks – 30% (loans); and farmers – 10% (upfront cost).
- D. *Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission (JNNSM), 2010* focuses on electricity generation from Solar energy, R&D and domestic manufacturing of the relevant

⁸² Sushanta K Chatterjee, *The Renewable Energy Policy Dilemma in India: Should Renewable Energy Certificate mechanism compete or merge with the Feed-in-Tariff Scheme?* (2017).

⁸³ Nidhi Srivastava, *Energy Law Lecture – Renewable Energy*, TERI SAS.

equipment. Initial target was 20GW which, in 2015, were enhanced to 100GW of solar power by 2022.

4.2. Legal Dimension

4.2.1. Strict Criteria of Patentability

Patent Law in India, as argued in the third chapter, is in conformity to TRIPS agreement and specifically to Article 27 of TRIPS. Therefore, there is no question of discrimination in terms of patentability of Green Technology. Every invention is analyzed on case by case basis on merits of Novelty, Inventive Step and Industrial Application. It has been observed that Inventive Step is the toughest step any invention has to face. As per Section 2(1) (ja) of Indian Patent Act, 1970 (as amended).

While one can argue that EST should be subject to protection like that of Section 3 (d) in case of Life Sciences related inventions to prevent evergreening of drugs with slight changes. However, ESTs are already subject to Section 2 (1) (j)⁸⁴ including the inventive step requirement. For an invention to have an Inventive Step as per Section 2(1) (ja)⁸⁵ it is required that the Invention involves improvement over the existing technologies which are usually mentioned in the specification and in the cited prior art by the respective patent offices. Further, such improvement has to be non-obvious to a person who is ordinarily, not exceptionally, skilled in the field to which the invention relates. The term ordinarily skilled in the art means that the person should not be an exceptionally skilled person like Einstein in Physics and requires only ordinary skill of the field of the invention. And such analysis has to be done keeping in mind when⁸⁶ the invention was filed, since. Therefore, Patent application are subject to tough test of Inventive Step as it is.

Non-Patentability as per Patent Act, 1970.

Section 3⁸⁷ weeds out any frivolous invention⁸⁸ from patentability. Invention that endangers “public morality or public order” are not patentable⁸⁹. Only application of scientific principles is patentable and not the principle per se⁹⁰. New uses of known process or product is not patentable⁹¹. Devices that could be created by re-arranging the already known elements therein

⁸⁴ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 2 (1) (j).

⁸⁵ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 2 (1) (ja).

⁸⁶ Examination of a patent application usually starts at least 48 months after filing of the application in India and in meantime the invention in application may become well known to public and examiner may feel that it is not inventive anymore. Therefore, date of filing is not only important to avoid anticipation and obtain or maintain priority date but also to establish Inventive Step itself.

⁸⁷ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3.

⁸⁸ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (a).

⁸⁹ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (b).

⁹⁰ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (c).

⁹¹ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (d).

functioning in an independent manner to each other are not patentable⁹². A “method of agriculture or horticulture” which is a type of EST is not patentable⁹³. There are many more non-patentability criteria mentioned in Section 3⁹⁴ and Section 4⁹⁵.

Therefore, it is argued that Patentability criteria is already very strict in India and does not need further changes.

4.2.2. Compulsory Licensing as a solution?

Compulsory Licensing is touted as another method by some of the scholars. However, others have argued that it would not result in an effective transfer of ESTs⁹⁶. Chapter XVI of Patent Act, 1970 provides for “General principles applicable to commercial working of granted Patents”⁹⁷ wherein it states that, “...the patentee or a person deriving title or interest on patent from the patentee shall not resort to practices which unreasonably restrain trade or adversely affect the international transfer of technology”⁹⁸. Therefore, it could be argued that compulsory licenses can be granted to ensure diffusion and transfer of ESTs into India.

As per Chapter XVI of Patent Act, 1970, a Compulsory License can only be granted after 3 years after the grant if “reasonable requirement of public is not met or the invention is not available at reasonable price or invention is not worked in territory of India”⁹⁹. Further, a person/entity seeking the Compulsory License has to prove to the Controller that best efforts were made to acquire the license and that person/entity has the technical & financial ability to work the invention to the advantage of the public¹⁰⁰. Further, Compulsory License so granted shall be make License holder liable to a reasonable quantum of royalty to be paid to the patentee. Still further, Compulsory licenses are subject to test of reasonableness as per TRIPS agreement and are a flexibility available only in exceptional cases, therefore, cannot be used as a norm. A blanket Compulsory License on ESTs would be further violative of Article 27 of the TRIPS agreement.

From above discussion it is clear that getting a Compulsory License is difficult. This difficulty can be substantiated by the fact that till date only one Compulsory License, the compulsory license granted related to cancer treating drug Nexavar following Bayer v. Natco judgement, has

⁹² The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (f).

⁹³ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3 (h).

⁹⁴ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 3.

⁹⁵ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 4.

⁹⁶ Nitya Nanda and Nidhi Srivastava, *Facilitating Technology Transfer for Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation*, TERI, https://www.teriin.org/projects/nfa/2008-2013/pdf/Facilitating_Tech_Transfer.pdf.

⁹⁷ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 83.

⁹⁸ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 83 (f).

⁹⁹ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 84 (1).

¹⁰⁰ The Patents Act, 1970, No. 39, Acts of Parliament, 1970 (India), § 84 (6).

been granted in India. Therefore, it is argued that solution to the problem does not lie in invoking compulsory licenses.

4.2.3 Evolving Laws

4.2.3.1. Patent Prosecution Highway

Recently, Ministry of Commerce released Draft Patent Amendment Rules, 2018 wherein Japanese PPH was envisioned. Herein, inter alia, applications taking priority from Japanese Patent Office shall be granted expedited examination which was earlier only to Start-ups and Applicants choosing Indian Patent office as International Searching Authority for their PCT applications. Further, it has been critically argued by the experts of the industry that after JPPH comes into force it would also mean that a Patent Application that has been granted by the Japanese patent Office will be quickly granted in India as well and, therefore, would dilute Indian criteria of patentability.

These fears can be allayed on the reasoning that, firstly, Japanese Patent Office will grant only bonafide inventions. Secondly, the Japanese and Indian Patent law has significant overlap as they both are signatories to TRIPS agreement that determines minimum standards of IPR. Thirdly, discretion to grant a patent shall ultimately rest with the Controller allotted on case by case basis who has to reason based on Indian Patent Law. Fourthly, an aggrieved person/entity can apply for pre grant opposition under Section 25 (1) or post grant opposition under Section 25 (2) or revocation of patent under Section 64.

While it is true that India has quite fewer patent applications originating within our territory that make their entry into Japan or any other country for that matter, so any sort of PPH tilts in the favour of the other country. However, we have to see PPH from geostrategic and trade angle. Japan and India are very strong trade partners. They have common geostrategic interests including counterbalancing rise of China. Japan has provided India with very good partnerships in Metro Rail projects which have been extremely successful. Therefore, it is hereby argued that PPH with Japan has been a very well thought decision of Government of India and would be beneficial as this would bring in further Japanese investment and expertise into India not only in traditional fields of technology but ESTs as well.

4.2.3.2. Commercial Working Data

Recently, Ministry of Commerce released Draft Patent Amendment Rules, 2019 wherein amendment to Form 27 has been suggested. Under the proposed amendment, the patentees, assignees of the patentees and/or licensees are exempt from disclosing quantity of invention

manufactured/imported in India, if the invention is not commercially worked measures taken to rectify it and the licensing activity undertaken during the year.¹⁰¹

In *Shamnad Basheer v. UoI Delhi* High court held that information under Form-27 is not confidential. High court held that: “Section 72 which requires these details to be part of a register which is open to public inspection”. The judgement highlighted that Commercial Working information should be made public as such information is crucial to achieve socio-economic welfare of the larger public.

The importance of commercial working data cannot be undermined for the ESTs. Such information can enable a potential manufacturer to get market information about working of the technology manufacturer is interested in. This information will bring more transparency in the system, will provide opportunity to the market to achieve healthy levels of competition and, above all, would enable policymakers to strategize what measures are needed to be taken for diffusion of ESTs into the Indian industry and market.

While conducting empirical research in the present research, it has been observed that Commercial Working data by way Form-27 is not properly filed in most of the applications as uploaded on the inPASS. The forms are usually left blank. It is herein proposed that improper filing of Form-27 should be ground for suspension of granted patent and which can be restored only by filing of Form-27.

4.2.4. Renewable Energy

India has a bicameral parliamentary system - Parliament has supreme law-making powers at the centre. Federal nature of governance is Basic structure of constitution of India. To better demarcate legislative powers various domains have been provided as entries by the Seventh Schedule of Constitution of India. The power sector (Electricity) is a concurrent subject provided in the Seventh Schedule (Entry 38 in concurrent list) of the Indian Constitution and hence both Centre and State have the power to regulate this domain. The Central Electricity Regulatory Commission and the respective State Electricity Regulatory Commission govern this domain. Earlier the Electricity Sector only witnessed public participation but gradually private players have also started taking interest in the same.¹⁰²

First mention of Renewable Energy in Electricity Act, 2003 is in Section 3¹⁰³ (National Electricity Policy and Plan) which states --- Section 3(1) “The Central Government shall, from time to time, prepare the *National Electricity Policy* and tariff policy, in consultation with the State Governments and the Authority for development of the power system based on optimal utilization of resources such as coal, natural gas, nuclear substances or materials, hydro and *renewable sources of energy*.”

¹⁰¹ Pankhuri Agarwal, *Indian Government Proposes to Dilute the Disclosure Requirement for Patent Working*, SPICYIP, <https://spicyip.com/2019/06/indian-government-proposes-govt-proposes-to-dilute-the-disclosure-requirement-for-patent-working.html>.

¹⁰² Nidhi Srivastava, *Energy Law Lecture – Renewable Energy*, TERI SAS.

¹⁰³ Electricity Act, 2003, No. 36, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India), § 3.

In Section 4 of Electricity Act, 2003¹⁰⁴, promotion for standalone systems for rural areas by use of non-conventional energy systems has been discussed: “The Central Government shall, after consultation with the State Governments, prepare and notify a national policy, permitting stand-alone systems (including those based on *renewable sources* of energy and other *non-conventional* sources of energy) for *rural areas*. Some steps have been taken upon this by the government and there shall be discussion about it later in the Chapter 6 – Conclusion.

Section 61 (Tariff regulations) states: “The Appropriate Commission shall, subject to the provisions of this Act, specify the terms and conditions for the determination of tariff, and in doing so, shall be guided by the following, namely:- (h) the promotion of co-generation and generation of electricity from renewable sources of energy.”¹⁰⁵ Thus, Renewable Energy generation shall be taken into account while determination of tariffs by SERCs.

Section 86 which deals with Functions of State Commission states: --- “(1) The *State Commission* shall discharge the following functions, namely: - (e) promote co-generation and generation of electricity from *renewable* sources of energy by providing suitable measures for *connectivity* with the *grid* and sale of electricity to any person, and also specify, for purchase of electricity from such sources, a *percentage* of the total consumption of electricity in the area of a distribution licensee.”¹⁰⁶ This is related to concept of RPO as discussed earlier in the chapter.

Case Law on RPOs: Hindustan Zinc Ltd vs Rajasthan Electricity Regulatory Commission

- Hindustan Zinc Ltd., Ambuja Cements Ltd etc. challenged the Rajasthan Electricity Regulatory Commission’s regulations on Renewable Purchase Obligations RERC with reasoning that the law¹⁰⁷ mandates application of RPOs on “total consumption in the area of the distribution licensee” and is not applicable to the captive power generators.
- SC held that:
 - “The impugned Regulations fall within the four corners of the Act of 2003 as well as Electricity Policy, 2005. The object of imposing RE Obligation is protection of environment and preventing pollution by utilizing Renewable Energy Sources as much as possible in larger public interest.”
 - “RPO cannot adversely affect the cost effectiveness of the Captive Power Plant. Moreover, the object being reduction of pollution by promoting renewable source of energy, larger public interest must prevail over the interest of the industry.”¹⁰⁸

Therefore, it is the view of the Apex court that larger public interest shall prevail over the interest of the industry.

¹⁰⁴ Electricity Act, 2003, No. 36, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India), § 4.

¹⁰⁵ Electricity Act, 2003, No. 36, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India), § 61(h).

¹⁰⁶ Electricity Act, 2003, No. 36, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India), § 86(1) (e).

¹⁰⁷ Electricity Act, 2003, No. 36, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India), § 86(1) (e).

¹⁰⁸ Nidhi Srivastava, *Energy Law Lecture – Renewable Energy*, TERI SAS.

Renewable Energy Implementation Strategy

While MNRE is responsible for Solar Energy, Wind Energy, Biomass Energy, Geothermal Energy, Tidal Energy, Small Hydro etc. Large Hydro was earlier kept under Ministry of Power but now has been transferred to MNRE recently. Critics may argue this transfer has been done to superficially increase share of renewables. Although there may be certain benefits of this as well by better integration between different renewables. For example, where dams can also be used to store energy generated by solar farms during day by reverse pumping water and using them later on during night. And to do this it is better to avoid cross ministry red-tapism.

While our main discussion has focused on Solar Energy above, it is important to not ignore the Wind energy potential. Target is to have 60GW of energy from wind by 2022. While solar power is available only during daytime in non-cloudy, non-smog and non-dust weather, Wind energy suffer from seasonal variation and other much more random fluctuations, mechanism of which are highly complex and leave even the most capable of weather scientist aided by their fancy supercomputers vulnerable to errors in their wind velocity forecasts where Climate Change is also causing change in wind velocity patterns which make prediction even more difficult.

Rest assured, even after all that intermittency talk on wind energy, wind energy is inarguably a better source of energy than Solar because it supplies power even during nighttime, and Wind energy can be easily stabilized by installing little higher capacity along with use of smart turbine management systems. Solar PV does have a one advantage over wind energy which we cannot ignore which is that Wind energy involves moving parts which means more wear& tear and thus more maintenance costs.

In an argument with Prof. Sethi¹⁰⁹, it was pointed out that his entire lecture was based on an assumption that we won't have any technology in the future that could store huge amount of energy to tackle this intermittency. Some energy storage systems that are already in place including pumping back water into dam which was already being done but has limitation in terms of Renewables being located far from dams and limitation in number of dams that can execute this backward pumping. Lithion ion based batteries are excruciatingly costly to make them feasible.

One interesting method that I came across was storing of electricity by the Swiss company EnergyVault in concrete blocks which are lifted to certain heights with help of huge electric cranes. And they are dropped when power demands surges and kinetic electricity is then harnessed to get energy. One major roadblock in this was higher cost of Concrete block itself. They solved this problem by purchasing dirt cheap construction debris from city and using them for concrete blocks.

A great method suggested by Prof Sethi¹¹⁰ was where he suggested using **Flexibility mechanism** to counter intermittency. Examples of Flexibility mechanism:

In Maharashtra, Farmers used to get electricity at night to pump their water pumps for irrigation purposes. The reason was because farmers don't pay, state in effort to minimize its losses provided them with cheap base load portion of electricity at around 3 AM. However, this caused

¹⁰⁹ Surya Prakash Sethi, *Lecture - Let's talk: Solar and Wind*, TERI SAS (23rd January, 2019).

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*

significant disturbance in the sleep cycle of the farmers and some even complained of snake bites because of the darkness. So, electricity generated by Solar Panels were given to villages directly which solved the problem. This is flexibility mechanism.

Another method is Solar Rooftop installation using smartgrid where users are billed based on net metering.

Yet another method is where Users were charged fixed fee to remain on connected to grid but energy is free if you install solar rooftops. This requires cost benefit analysis and PPP project implementation.

Still another method could be usage of Solar Thermals instead of Solar PVs. Solar PVs require rare earth metals which are in short supply. Battery storage is a new concept but storing heated water for industrial processes is a well-known technology. So, Solar thermals could store electricity in water heat itself instead of using batteries.

Way forward in Renewable Energy Law and Policy

“We can increase Public Private Partnerships in renewables by providing for framework for Participation specifically for Renewables. Other measures for promotion of renewables could be fiscal and other support for Investors to keep the tariffs affordable, move towards competitively determined tariffs in Solar and wind, develop eco-system for decentralized and off-grid solutions for improved energy access, strengthen and incentivise Intra State and Inter State transmission infrastructure, progressive focus on improving generation efficiencies and strengthening Institutional framework.”¹¹¹ PPPs could solve multiple bottlenecks in creating a well-oiled industrial infrastructure for Solar and Wind systems, including technical know-how, labor skills, financial viability, efficiency in organization of the industry and depoliticization of industry by instilling efficiency based on market structure.

4.3. Summary of Chapter 4

Chapter 4 discusses relation between Policy of Indian government, Indian Patent laws, Renewable Energy related laws, Renewable Energy related policy and Transfer of ESTs from Indian Perspective. NAPCC, 2008 created 8 missions to mitigate and adapt to the climate change. NAPCC was a trigger for many other policies including RPOs as part of Electricity Generation and Distribution systems.

Patents have a very strict criteria of Inventive Step. Further, Indian Patent Laws are in line with the TRIPS as a whole and specific its Article 27. Non-Patentability criteria mentioned in the Section 3 and 4 read with section 2(1) (j) and 2(1) (ja) makes sure that only Bona fide invention are granted patents. While Compulsory Licensing and/or inclusion of ESTs into Section 3 has been argued by some scholars as a way of boosting India’s renewable energy equipment manufacturing sector, the present research argues against it.

While there are many critics of JPPH, the present research argue that it is well thought out move. The present research further suggests PPH as a mechanism of leveraging ESTs diffusion into India, more about which is discussed in summary and suggestions of Chapter 5. The present

¹¹¹ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

research criticizes Draft Amendment of Patent Rules, 2019 which liberalizes Form 27 requirements and dilutes requirement of disclosure of information regarding commercial working of the patent after the grant. The said amendment moves in the direction of lesser transparency which is never a good idea. It is argued that while this information is a motivator for inventor to commercial work an invention as failure to do so may attract Compulsory Licensing, another use of such data is increased competition in the market as licensing information, worth of invention worked is disclosed which is closely monitored by all the stakeholders.

RPOs have a significant effect on Renewable Energy production. RPOs cater to the larger public interest which shall prevail over the interests of the industry. Intermittency is a big shortcoming of the renewable energy. Unless energy storage systems like EnergyVault's concrete storage system, fuel cell or solar to ethanol, etc. are made practical and cost effective, intermittency will remain an issue. Flexibility mechanisms are one method to overcome the issue of intermittency examples of which have been described in detail in the chapter. Solar rooftop based on net metering and smart grid is a new age technique which can be used under the SPIN scheme to improve EST implementation. Integrated models and hybrid renewable systems could be another way forward.

Hybrid renewables systems, in an embodiment, includes solar thermal, solar pv and wind turbine which can be used simultaneously or alternatively based on the demand at a particular point of time.

5. EMPIRICAL RESEARCH

The present research will rely on empirical analysis to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions. Data will be collected from only Public Patent Database; no paid or proprietary databases will be used. Primary source of data shall be the patent search of Indian Patent Office also known as inPASS or Indian Patent Advanced Search System. inPASS is available at url: <http://ipindiaservices.gov.in/publicsearch>.

5.1. Importance of Patent Search and its types

Patent search is very powerful tool that can help anyone and everyone pursuing whatever careers. If one is a scientific researcher Patent Search will provide that researcher with knowledge about already existing technologies upon which the research work can be added upon. Further, it would avoid re-creation of already existing technologies and avoid duplicity of the research. It can provide the said scientific researcher idea about shortcomings in the existing technologies and thereafter in which field carrying out the research could be beneficial to the society.

If the entity is a manufacturing company that wishes to secure its interest in the market and get patents for its advancement over existing technologies, it should first query what is the existing technology. Only then can it can get a patent over existing prior art.

If the entity is a local business and lack the R&D capacity then the entity can choose to simply carry out a patent search and find out technologies that have recently expired and free to use. In fact, any business carrying entity can improve quality of the products and services offered by using the patented technologies whose lifetime have expired to improve upon their businesses. If the entity is a restaurant for example it can use patented methods that can improve the taste of the food. An automobile spare part manufacturer can improve the quality of its products by using expired patents.

Even individuals can in their daily lifestyle can improve their life. For example, a person interested in achieving better gardening may use expired patents to improve the quality and quantity of the garden produce. And perhaps while using the method given in the expired patent the said individual may get an idea to improve upon that technology and realize that (s)he in fact has made a new invention and could reap the benefits of this intellectual creation by getting patents for it.

Patent Search is therefore is an exceptional tool that cannot be ignored by any individual or entity that wishes to achieve excellence.

Basic types of Patent Searches are:

1. *Prior Art Search/ Patentability Search*: This type of Patent search is often carried out by the Patent Offices after they receive a patent application. The Patent Office will cite closest prior arts that may destroy the novelty and/or inventive step of the alleged invention. Thereafter, the applicant will proceed to show how the alleged invention is novelty and inventive step by showing the differences. The importance of carrying out

this search with good quality cannot be underestimated. As conducting a poor search may enable mere innovations or already known inventions to get a patent and, therefore, discourage the bonafide researchers to create new inventions beneficial for societies as patentability criteria becomes lower.

2. *Invalidation Search/Freedom to Operate search*: This type of search is carried out by an entity who wishes to use the technology of its competitor without paying the licensing fee. The search is carried out by skilled searchers to find out technologies existing prior to date of filing of application to which patent was granted to the competitor. Doing so will lead to revocation of the granted patent and then the entity would be free to use the technologies without any fear of infringement suits.
3. *Validation Search*: This type of search is taken up by a potential applicant of a new technology. Validation search may be carried out to ensure that time and money is not wasted in creating an invention that has no scope of getting a patent grant. It may give an insight to R&D institution to improve upon the research to suitably avoid any objections at the prosecution stage of the patent.
4. *State of the Art Search/Landscape Search*: This type of search is carried out by scientific and industrial researchers to figure out the areas where there exist sufficient lacunae to create a new technology so that utilization of investments is done in efficient manner and risk of failure is minimized.

5.2 Classification of Inventions

Classification of technologies into categories plays a crucial role in the patent search. Classification is a method of categorizing the inventions into various types based on their uses and physical components. There are millions of preexisting technologies and if any meaningful Patent Search has to be carried out it has to be divided into classes so that search results can be narrowed into a more relevant results since it is humanely impossible to read thousands of results 99% of which are going to simply belong to other category. For example, an invention related to a capacitor used in electronics equipment cannot be possibly infringed by a new recipe of a pasta.

“The International Patent Classification (IPC), established by the Strasbourg Agreement 1971, provides for a hierarchical system of language independent symbols for the classification of patents and utility models according to the different areas of technology to which they pertain. A new version of the IPC enters into force each year on January 1.”¹¹² IPC divides all the inventions into 8 types i.e.

- A. “Human Necessities
- B. Performing Operations; Transporting,
- C. Chemistry; Metallurgy
- D. Textiles; Paper
- E. Fixed Constructions
- F. Mechanical Engineering; Lighting; Heating; Weapons; Blasting
- G. Physics

¹¹² *International Patent Classification (IPC)*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, <https://www.wipo.int/classifications/ipc/en/>.

H. Electricity”¹¹³

Wherein A-H are Section titles which are followed by class, sub-class, group and subgroup. Given below (fig. 9)¹¹⁴ is an example of such classification:

Example:

inPASS provides an option for searching the inventions based on IPC system of classification.

5.3. Methodology

Although Methodology has been explained in the first chapter. It shall be now explained in detail the choices that was available during the research, selecting the best choices and explaining the reasons for all the decisions taken herein. First and foremost, it has to be noted that inPASS allows to search based on date of filing which means we should narrow down our search by restricting the search only to those applications which have will still be active. Thus, searching for patent applications filed on or before 31 May 1999 will be futile as lifetime of a patent is 20 years. Date upto which search will be carried out shall be 01 June 2019.

5.3.1. Selection of ESTs

Firstly, types of ESTs will be discussed in summary manner as it has already been discussed in detail in second chapter. ESTs are “technologies that protect the environment, are less polluting, use all resources in a more sustainable manner, recycle more of their wastes and products, and handle residual wastes in a more acceptable manner than the technologies for which they were substitutes and are compatible with nationally determined socio-economic, cultural and environmental priorities”¹¹⁵. ESTs have been divided into two basic types viz hard technologies and soft technologies based on whether direct implementation of invention is being done or are they knowledge based. Another method of classification of the ESTs is categorizing them based on the time period they were developed. Based on this classification there are 4 types of ESTs: traditional, modern, high and future technology. ¹¹⁶

¹¹³ *Guide to the International Patent Classification*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/export/sites/www/classifications/ipc/en/guide/guide_ipc.pdf.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁵ Richard J.T. Klein et al., *Application of environmentally sound technologies for adaptation to climate change*, UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE, <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/docs/2006/tp/tp02.pdf>.

¹¹⁶ *Ibid.*

While the above said classification is great for discussion and qualitative analysis, it doesn't server purpose of the empirical research sought in the present research. We need classification-based division of ESTs to effectively search any Patent Database. We will, therefore, look towards the "IPC Green Inventory" which classifies ESTs into 7 broad categories.

For the purposes of present research we will be focusing on two technologies.

1. Generation of Power from Solar Energy – Photovoltaic or Thermal or other method.
2. Generation of Power from Wind Energy.

The reason for clubbing of Photovoltaic and Thermal generation of power has been mentioned under the head 5.3.5. Assumptions and Limitations.

5.3.1.1. Classification criteria - IPC Green Inventory

The technologies that have been considered as ESTs by the UNFCCC have been divided in 7 following broad categories by the IPC Committee of Experts: Alternative Energy Production; Transportation; Energy Conservation; Waste management; Agriculture/Forestry; Administrative, regulatory and design aspects; and Nuclear Power generation. And these are further classified into subtypes in hierarchical manner. The present research will look into onlt the first type i.e. Alternate Energy Production.

Alternative Energy Production include Bio-fuels, Fuel cells, Gasification of biomass, Harnessing energy from manmade waste, Hydro, Ocean thermal, Wind, Solar, Geothermal and Muscle energy sources etc. Our research is going to focus on ESTs related to generation/production of electricity or harvesting of Solar and Wind Energy by all means possible.

Alternate Energy production Solar energy as per IPC Green Inventory in the IPC classification belongs to F024S and H024S and Wind energy as per IPC Green Inventory in the IPC classification belongs to F03D. Therefore, we will try the search in these 3 classifications using inPASS.

Search results obtained without restricting the date of filing of application or any other search parameter are as follows. Number of applications filed:

1. F24S – 2 Applications till date.
2. H24S – 0 (Zero) Applications till date.
3. F03D – 294 applications till date.

A simple "solar power" query resulted in thousands of results, exact number of which will be discussed later in the chapter. Further F03D latest patent application was that 3 June 2016. Whereas, as per Section 11A of the Indian Patent Act,1970 (as amended) and corresponding Rule 24 of the Patent Rules, 2003 (as amended) an application is published automatically within one

month of expiry of statutory 18-month period. Thus, all applications from period of 3 June 2016 to 1 December 2017 are not visible in the IPC classification-based search. And there may be even some applications which are filed after

The reason is quite clear. IPC classification is not properly entered into that database of inPASS. Further, when we open application status of any patent application, there is no mention of the IPC classification anywhere. It is further to be noted that nowhere in Indian Patent Act or Rules or the Manual of Patent office Practice and Procedure (MPPPP) requires an applicant to mention the IPC classification. Further, it is noted that India is not a member to the Strasbourg Agreement by which IPC emanates¹¹⁷. However, it is only informally used by the Indian Patent Office. And furthermore, existence of IPC classification-based search tab on inPASS suggests that India will ratify this agreement in the future.

Further, classification of IPC Green inventory has not been finalized. F24J, F03G and H01L are some the classes observed to have been not included while should have been included in the IPC Green inventory.

Therefore, for the present research IPC classification-based research on inPASS is futile. A quick search on Patentscope showed good results which could be further narrowed with keyword-based search. However, Patentscope has limitations for the present research, reasons for which are discussed in the section below.

5.3.2. Selection of Patent Database for Search

Since the present research is focused on ESTs in India, choice of inPASS is a no brainer. inPASS or Indian Patent Advanced Search System is a free Public database of Indian Patent Office. inPASS is crucial not only for search but also for Prosecution of patents by the applicants.

Patentscope is the public database search system of WIPO which is one of the best search systems that are in public domain. WIPO has in 2018 integrated data of Indian patent database into Patentscope. However, there are some issues of data updation on Patentscope related to Indian applications. Further, documents are not available on Global Dossier. Still further, Patent Search cannot be narrowed based on status of application i.e. granted or published. Even still further, WIPO has no responsibility to ensure correctness of the data whereas it is IPOs responsibility to ensure correctness of data uploaded on inPASS.

It is for these reasons that Patent Database chosen for patent search is inPASS.

¹¹⁷ *WIPO-Administered Treaties*, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/showresults.jsp?lang=en&treaty_id=11.

5.3.3. Usage of Operators

The list of operators available on inPASS are as follows¹¹⁸:

- * or the Asterisk sign: Usage of * signifies zero, single or any number of characters
- ~ or the tiled sign: Signifies only one alphabet or numeral or so
- + or addition symbol: Signifies that the results containing word used after + shall be included in the search. But if + is used 2 times then only results containing both words will be shown.
- - or subtraction symbol: Signifies that results containing the word used after - shall not be included in the search
- “” or quotation marks: Its usage yields search results containing the exact mentioned word. If two words are mentioned within quotes separated by a space then search results which have both exact words shall be included in the results however, they can be in any order but could be separated by numerous characters therein.
- AND OR NOT operators or Boolean operators: AND means search results containing all of the words will be included. OR means search results will include all the results containing either of the words and NOT means the if the words written after the operator is in the application it will be excluded from the search result.

inPASS has certain shortcomings in terms of operators:

- The operator NEAR available in Patentscope and other good databases is not available.
- Quotation with two words doesn't search for 2 words separated by a space but rather works like an AND operator.
- Boolean operators i.e. AND, OR, NOT do not work on inPASS by entering them into the keyword query itself. They have to be selected from dropdown menu. Therefore, makes search a cumbersome process¹¹⁹.

5.3.4. Keyword selection and Final Search Queries

Keyword based search will be the prime method of attaining the results of empirical analysis in the present research. Keyword selection is the one of the most important aspect of the Patent Searches. It is so because for a given technology multiple terms may exist. For example, a technology may be called *harvesting energy from sun* or *harvesting solar energy*. Both will mean the same invention. It is to be noted that present research will search in title of the invention only. Ideally it is suggested that Abstract of the invention to obtain better quality of search results. However, the lack of NEAR operator makes searching abstract a rather poor option.

¹¹⁸ Search Syntax, INDIAN PATENT OFFICE, <http://ipindiaservices.gov.in/PublicSearch/PublicationSearch/Help>.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*

NEAR operator enables to search for applications containing the two keywords separated by a maximum of predefined number of characters. This is useful in abstract based search.

We will now proceed with Query selection for Title based search. Following search queries have been rejected for the reasons given below:

- *Solar Power*: Using this search is not advisable as thousands of search results are shown using words Solar or Power. Almost acting how OR operator is supposed to work.
- **Solar*Power**: Also shows results like solar *powered* devices. Therefore, shows results which are not related to power generation. Further, shows only inventions in which solar keyword comes before power keyword. While using of **Power*Solar** with dropdown operator OR could have solved this issue solar *powered* devices would still be shown.
- *“Solar Power”*: While this query would most likely get the right results but for the sake of using the operators the right way without exploiting any bug in the implementation the patent search system, this query is also rejected.
- *Electricity*: The keyword electricity has been ignored because virtually no results were added by using this keyword.
- *Photovoltaics*: Use of keyword Photovoltaic/ Photovoltaics resulted in poor search results. The technologies that involve use of Photovoltaics doesn't always use the keyword Photovoltaics in the title.

The major issue faced while using only a single string like +solar +power is the loss of relevant search results. Following strings have been found to provide best quality results.

1. +solar +power
2. +solar +thermal
3. +solar +generation
4. +sun +harvesting

Therefore 4 strings are kept used with Boolean operator OR.

Given below is the screenshot (fig. 10)¹²⁰ of the search query used for solar power search on inPASS to derive search results for published applications for duration of 1st June 1999 to 1st June 2019 for search string:

(+solar +power) OR (+sun +harvesting) OR (+solar +thermal) OR (+solar +generation)

¹²⁰ Indian Patent Advanced Search System, INDIAN PATENT OFFICE, <http://ipindiaservices.gov.in/PublicSearch>.

Patent Search

Patent Search Patent E-register Application Status Help

Publication Type: Published Granted

Select Search Field: Application Date (National) From Date (MM/dd/yyyy): 06/01/1999 To Date (MM/dd/yyyy): 06/01/2019 Select Logical Operator: AND

Select Search Field: Title Please Enter Title: +solar +power Select Logical Operator: OR

Select Search Field: Title Please Enter Abstract: +sun +harvesting Select Logical Operator: OR

Select Search Field: Title Please Enter Complete Specification: +solar +thermal Select Logical Operator: OR

Select Search Field: Title Please Enter Application Number: +solar +generation Select Logical Operator: OR

Final Search Query for title-based search of Generation of power from solar energy is:
 (+solar +power) OR (+sun +harvesting) OR (+solar +thermal) OR (+solar +generation)

Final Search Query for title-based search of Generation of power from wind energy is:
 (+wind +power) OR (+wind +turbine)

The advantages of using the above stated search queries are:

1. Only Generation of power from solar or wind energy are covered since “Powered” is eliminated by used of + operator.
2. Chances of other related technologies like transmission, storage etc. of solar or wind energy/power are eliminated because the search query has been used in the Title.
 - a. As per Rule 13(7)(a) of Indian Patent Rules (as amended) Title cannot be longer than 15 words. Out of which 2 words have to be used from our search query, remaining words would be lost in grammatical construction of the title.
 - b. Controller also expect that the Title should explain the purpose of inventions which generally eats away 4-5 words.
 - c. Further, it is a matter of general practice that title of the invention, opening of the description and the preamble of the main independent claim are kept consistent. And Indian Patent Office generally does not allow multiple independent claims unless they fall under the ambit of Single Inventive Concept as per Section 10(5) of the Indian Patent Act, 1970 (as amended).
3. The search query used above has provided with quality results based on comparison with other search strings which were tried by way of various permutations and combinations.

5.3.5. Assumptions and Limitations

IPC Green Inventory is still in developmental stage and list is not exhaustive. Further, classification of Invention traditionally has been done based on their physical characteristics and functionalities. Thus, amendments are required in entire IPC to organize them in line with EST classification. This process is bound to take a lot many years of research, deliberations and stakeholder consultation. And without proper classification for ESTs it is tough to carry out an accurate patent search.

IPC classification has not been properly entered into that database of inPASS. There is no mention of the IPC classification when application status of an application is opened. It is further to be noted that nowhere in Indian Patent Act or Rules or the Manual of Patent office Practice and Procedure (MPPPP) requires an applicant to mention the IPC classification. Further, it is noted that India is not a member to the Strasbourg Agreement by which IPC emanates¹²¹. However, it is only informally used by the Indian Patent Office. However, existence of IPC classification-based search tab on inPASS suggests that India will ratify this agreement in the future.

Some applications which were filed in India after 1 December 2017 are not likely to have been published. Since 18-month statutory duration as per Rule 24 of Indian Patent Rules, 2003 (as amended) has not lapsed for them and very few applicants choose for early publication under Rule 24A of Indian Patent Rules, 2003 (as amended).

While a lot of effort has gone into derivation of the Final Search Query. No query is free from fault. Furthermore, it takes decades of Practice to derive an efficient search result for a patent search. This is also why use of OR Boolean operator has been chosen in the Final search query because use of such query would minimize the loss of good search results.

While searching for the Solar Thermal and Solar Photovoltaics separately it was observed that some technologies involved use of both technologies. Some technologies were circuits which were usable for both the systems. Some technologies were hybrid systems which involved use of both technologies. Further, doing so would simplify already complex research.

Lack of NEAR operator on inPASS has forced us to restrict us to title-based search. However, title-based search has its own merits. As explained in the section above¹²². Title based search gives accurate results with drawback of missing out on a small fraction of technologies which could have been unveiled in the abstract-based search.

Further since e-filing and maintenance of records digitally has only recently improved in the Indian Patent Office. Search Results for period of around and before 2000 could not be trusted.

The assumption that will be core to the research is number of filings are proportional to number of grants, in terms of nationality analysis and yearly trend analysis.

¹²¹ WIPO-Administered Treaties, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION, https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ShowResults.jsp?lang=en&treaty_id=11.

¹²² 5.3.4. *Keyword selection and Final Search Queries* heading of the present research.

5.4. Data and its Analysis

Search Query for title-based search of Generation of power from solar energy is:

(+solar +power) OR (+sun +harvesting) OR (+solar +thermal) OR (+solar +generation)

A total of 563 applications have been filed in the above-mentioned search query from 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019. Latest applications may not have been published. Out of these meagre a of 21 have been granted. This means a meagre 3.7% of applications have been granted. Others are either pending, rejected, abandoned or withdrawn. This proves the assertion made in the chapter 4 regarding strict criteria of patentability. Further, India has only solar equipment assembly, solar equipment manufacturing industry is virtually absent in India. China dominates the manufacturing of these components.

Search Query for title-based search of Generation of power from wind energy is:

(+wind +power) OR (+wind +turbine)

A total of 2418 applications have been filed in the above-mentioned search query from 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019. Latest applications may not have been published. Out of these meagre a of 329 have been granted. This means 13.6% of applications have been granted. Others are either pending, rejected, abandoned or withdrawn. This yet again proves the assertion made in the chapter 4 regarding strict criteria of patentability. However, the number of filing and percentage of grants witness a substantial rise in comparison of solar energy despite usage of a rather simpler and less broad search query for wind energy. The reason is that wind turbine manufacturing is picking up in India and this is in the backdrop of China's inability to penetrate the global market. Further, as per "Tulsi Tanti, Chairman and Managing Director of Suzlon Energy", Renewable energy Purchase Obligation (RPO) has been a game changer for the industry.¹²³ Senvion, a German company has been reported to moving its manufacturing from Germany to India.¹²⁴ Further, it has been argued that manufacturing of Wind Turbines has a tendency of being localized as Wind turbines are rather bulky in nature, therefore, increases the cost of production. Further, online auctioning using reverse bidding process have led to significant cost reductions and therefore healthy supply chain structure has been created in the wind energy industry in India.

The year 1999 starts from 1 June 1999 and ends on 31 December 1999. Similarly, 2019 starts on 1 January 2019 but ends on 1 June 2019 to keep them within research timeline. All other years are full years. Year 2018 and 2019 will show only publications that have been published on expedited basis by express request on Form 9 under Rule 24A of the Indian Patent Rules, 2003 (as amended). Table below (Table 2) shows yearly trends for the number of applications filed for Solar and Wind power generation technologies based on keyword search of title.

¹²³ M Ramesh, *In turbine manufacturing, wind blowing the India way*, THE HINDU BUSINESS LINE, <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/companies/in-turbine-manufacturing-wind-blowing-the-india-way/article9681051.ece>.

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*

Year	No. of Applications filed – Solar	No. of Applications filed – Wind
1999	00	00
2000	01	04
2001	01	09
2002	00	12
2003	02	22
2004	01	32
2005	01	27
2006	05	59
2007	09	51
2008	14	106
2009	22	214
2010	27	288
2011	57	330
2012	69	219
2013	83	176
2014	66	161
2015	50	157
2016	44	191
2017	58	169
2018	38	154
2019	16	37

The sharp rise in patenting activity during 2009 to 2013 can be attributed to NAPCC targets set in 2008 (fig. 11¹²⁵ given below) and increased focus of government in RPO.

¹²⁵ P.C. Maithani, *Renewable Energy Development in India*, INDIAN SOLAR ALLIANCE.

Further Indian economy showed relative stability despite global slowdown which could have attracted patent activity from abroad. Further it has to be kept in mind that phase 1 of JNNSM had a timeline of 2010 to 2013. And while after 2012 Wind energy patenting activity has largely sustained the same levels of patenting, solar energy has failed to do so.

Also, patent activity of Solar is very smaller in number to wind energy. While it could be due to the advantages of wind energy discussed as above. Or it could also be because of relative simplicity in manufacturing of Wind energy equipment. Further, the fact that India has a strong manufacturing ecosystem for automobile sector could have played a big role as both are mechanical devices. Further, one reason could be that there is a huge scope of improvement in technologies if they are mechanical devices like Wind turbines, however, this scope gets very limited in solar thermal and solar photovoltaics. Solar Thermal have inventive scope either in mirror arrangement or in heat storage systems both which are century old technologies and thus scope for improvement is little. In Solar PVs Semiconductor based properties are very well known and only few new technologies like thin film are arriving to challenge them. However, thin film technology is costly and thus cannot replace Solar PVs. Therefore, they have no commercial usage and thus no patenting activity can be derived from here as well. While graphene and nanoparticles has opened way for new technologies for Solar but they are futuristic in nature.

Types of Applications and Applicants' nationality – Solar

We will study granted technologies obtained in the search string to find solutions for diffusion of these technologies. 21 technologies were obtained in the search earlier which were granted for Solar Energy generation which were filed in time period of 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019. Please note that Nationality of Applicant is important here and not of the inventor as inventor has already assigned all the rights to the Applicant by way of either executed Form 1 or assignment deed. See table below for the aforementioned analysis (Table 3).

Type of Applicant	Nationality of Applicant	No. of Patents
Individual	Indian	2
Commercial Entity	Indian	1
PSU	Indian	1
CSIR or IIT	Indian	6
Research/Educational Institute	USA	1
Commercial Entity	USA	3
Commercial Entity	German	1
Commercial Entity (TVP Solar)	Swiss	3
Commercial Entity	Malta	1
European Space Agency	EP	1
Commercial Entity	Danish	1

Therefore, 10 out of 21 Patents have their origin in India itself which is almost 47%. Whereas, as per 2016-17 annual report patent filings with Indian Applicants was only up to 30%¹²⁶. Therefore, there is clear lack of interest by foreign companies for filing in India. TVP Solar, a Swiss company alone has 3 patent grants in India. Europe as a whole has 7 patents attributable to it which is 33%. USA has 4 Patents. China, interestingly has no patents at all.

Types of Applications and Applicants' nationality – Wind

While we have analyzed all the granted patents for Solar energy based on search query because they were in really small numbers to begin with. But wind energy has 329 granted patents in the search query (+wind +power) OR (+wind +turbine) in period from 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019. Also, it would be a futile exercise to analyze the patents which have already lost 10 years of their life. The present research will, therefore, analyze only recent granted patents which have at least 10 years of life term remaining of the total life of 20 years. We are therefore analyzing granted patents filed on or after 1 January 2010. See table below for the aforementioned analysis (Table 4).

Type of Applicant	Nationality of Applicant	No. of Patents
Individual	Indian	1
Commercial Entity	Indian	2
PSUs	Indian	0
CSIR or IIT	Indian	1
Commercial Entity	Taiwan	1
Commercial Entity	USA	1
Commercial Entity	German	10
Commercial Entity	Swiss	1
Individual	Hungary	1
Commercial Entity (Gamesa)	Spain	3
Commercial Entity (Vestas Wind Systems A/S)	Danish	23
Commercial Entity (LM Glasfiber A/S)	Danish	6
Commercial Entity	Danish	1
Commercial Entity	Japanese	3
Commercial Entity	Estonia	1
Commercial Entity	S. Korea	2

Danish entities alone have 30 patents granted out of which Vestas Wind Systems A/S has 23 patents and LM Glasfiber A/S has 6 patents. Danish companies alone account for 52.63% of granted patents.

¹²⁶ The Office of the Controller General of Patents Designs Trademarks and Geographical Indications, *Annual Report 2016-17*, INDIAN PATENT OFFICE, http://www.ipindia.nic.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOAnnualReport/1_94_1_1_79_1_Annual_Report-2016-17_English.pdf.

Major German entities filing Wind energy Patents are: Siemens, Suzlon and Senvion. Senvion has 4 granted patents vide patent numbers 284022, 296773, 287163 and 307680 – Interestingly all these patents were filed in 2010 in India and have a 2008 German priority which should be around the time company most probably made strategic move of shifting its manufacturing to India¹²⁷. Spain's **Gamesa Innovation & Technology, S.I. has 3 granted Patents**. Japanese giants like Toshiba also have filed many applications.

Indian PSUs have *ZERO* granted patents. Indian government should provide funding for domestic R&D. India's company called Wind care India Ltd has 2 granted patents. In total, India has 3 patents out of 57 granted patents which is 5.26%. Whereas, as per 2016-17 annual report patent filings with Indian Applicants was only up to 30%¹²⁸. Relying on importation of technologies is a very dangerous trend. Nowhere in the world, the industry has succeeded without homegrown R&D. 5.26% value is really alarming.

5.5. Results and findings

Since the resent research is related to patents it has been found befitting that results of the empirical research be shown as if claims for an application of patent were being drafted.

I claim:

1. A fact of very low number of solar patent filing in India, *characterized in that*, patent filings in technologies related to generation and/or utilization of solar is also quite lower, wherein the main reason for such shortfall, in an embodiment, could be that multinationals simply don't see India as gaining manufacturing activities in solar and wind anytime soon, and *in that*, the multinationals focus on patenting inventions in jurisdictions wherein manufacturing of that sector is located, wherein curbing infringement in these jurisdictions would be sufficient to curb the infringement worldwide.
2. The fact of very low number of solar patent filing in India as claimed in claim 1, *wherein*, a meagre of 563 applications for the search query “(+solar +power) OR (+sun +harvesting) OR (+solar +thermal) OR (+solar +generation)” were filed in India from 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019 with a very low grant rate of 3.7%.
3. The fact of very low number of solar patent filing in India as claimed in claim 1, *wherein*, a rise in patenting activity was observed in period of 2009 to 2013 which is attributable to JNNSM phase 1 and RPO.
4. A fact of relatively larger number of wind energy patent filing in India, *characterized in that*,

¹²⁷ “In August 2016, Senvion acquired the production facilities at Baramati, Maharashtra from Kalyani group.”

¹²⁸ The Office of the Controller General of Patents Designs Trademarks and Geographical Indications, *Annual Report 2016-17*, INDIAN PATENT OFFICE, http://www.ipindia.nic.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOAnnualReport/1_94_1_1_79_1_Annual_Report-2016-17_English.pdf.

wind turbines have a tendency of being localized as Wind turbines are rather bulky in nature, therefore, increases the cost of production.

5. The fact of relatively larger number of wind energy patent filing in India as claimed in claim 4, *wherein*, a number of 2418 applications for the search query “(+wind +power) OR (+wind +turbine)” were filed in India from 1 June 1999 to 31 May 2019 with a high grant rate of 13.6%.
6. The fact of relatively larger number of wind energy patent filing in India as claimed in claim 4, *wherein*, wind energy patenting activity is attributable to inability of China to capture global market in this sector.
7. The fact of relatively larger number of wind energy patent filing in India as claimed in claim 4, *wherein*, India has a strong manufacturing base for mechanical devices as seen in automobile industry success story.
8. A spike in patenting activity is observed in duration 2009 to 2013, *characterized in that*, at least one government policy has caused this spike.
9. The spike in patenting activity is observed in duration 2009 to 2013, as claimed in claim 8, *wherein*, such spike is attributable to the government policy of the adoption of NAPCC in 2008 and/or Renewable Purchase obligations.
10. The spike in patenting activity is observed in duration 2009 to 2013, as claimed in claim 8 or 9, *wherein*, such governmental policy is further influenced by international deliberations and treaties, in an embodiment, UNFCCC framework.
11. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Solar Energy, *characterized in that*, almost half the granted patents belong to Indian entities, and *in that* remaining patents mostly belong to U.S.A. and Europe.
12. The set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Solar Energy as claimed in claim 11, *wherein*, CSIR holds 24% of patents.
13. The set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Solar Energy as claimed in claim 11, *wherein*, Europe as a whole has 7 patents attributable to it which is 33% of total granted patents.
14. The set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Solar Energy as claimed in claim 11, *wherein*, 10 out of 21 Patents have their origin in India itself which is almost 47%. Whereas, as per 2016-17 annual report patent filings with Indian Applicants was only up to 30% which shows that there is clear lack of interest by foreign companies for filing in India.
15. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy, *characterized in that*, almost half the granted patents belong to Danish entities, and *in that* patents mostly belong to Europe.
16. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 15, *wherein*, Danish entities alone have 30 patents granted out of which Vestas Wind Systems A/S has 23 patents and LM Glasfiber A/S has 6 patents, further *wherein*, Danish companies alone account for 52.63% of granted patents.

17. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 15, *wherein*, Major German entities filing Wind energy Patents are: Siemens, Suzlon and Senvion.
18. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 18, *wherein*, Senvion has 4 granted patents vide patent numbers 284022, 296773, 287163 and 307680, all of which these patents were filed in 2010 in India and have a 2008 German priority, which could be an indication that around the time company most probably made strategic move of shifting its manufacturing to India
19. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 15, *wherein*, Spain's **Gamesa Innovation & Technology, S.I. has 3 granted Patents.** Japanese giants like Toshiba also have filed many applications.
20. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 15, *wherein*, Indian PSUs have *ZERO* granted patents. India's company called Wind care India Ltd has 2 granted patents. In total, India has 3 patents out of 57 granted patents which is 5.26%. Whereas, as per 2016-17 annual report patent filings with Indian Applicants was only up to 30%¹²⁹.
21. A set of data regarding nationality of applicants of Wind Energy as claimed in claim 20, *wherein* Indian government should take measures like providing direct funding for domestic R&D since relying on importation of technologies is a very dangerous trend and since nowhere in the world, the industry has succeeded without homegrown R&D.

5.6. Summary of Chapter 5

Patent Search is an important tool, inter alia, for researchers, patent seekers and license seekers. Importance of good database cannot be underestimated. A good patent search database enables Examiners to prepare a good patentability report which could avoid post grant blushes to the Controller, or could provide crucial information to Researchers by which they can focus on which field should they research more on.

Characterized in That is a phrase generally used in Independent claims, wherein anything mentioned before such phrase is an invention which is already well known. Therefore, it is hereby suggested that Indian R&D Institutions should first try to innovate and work upon the technologies by discovering such prior arts.

Classification of technologies into categories plays a crucial role in the patent search. Classification is a method of categorizing the inventions into various types based on their uses and physical components. Classification is crucial for getting quality results in the patent search. inPASS provides an option for searching the inventions based on IPC system of classification.

¹²⁹ The Office of the Controller General of Patents Designs Trademarks and Geographical Indications, *Annual Report 2016-17*, INDIAN PATENT OFFICE, http://www.ipindia.nic.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOAnnualReport/1_94_1_1_79_1_Annual_Report-2016-17_English.pdf.

For the purposes of present research, we will be focusing on two technologies, Generation of Power from Solar Energy – Photovoltaic or Thermal or other method and Generation of Power from Wind Energy.

IPC Green Inventory's classification-based search yielded poor results for reasons discussed in the chapter. Therefore, this style of search had to be discarded. inPASS has been chosen over Patentscope as Public Database for Patent Search for reason mentioned therein. Then after a lot of research work and deliberation, using reasoned hit and trials relevant search query string was obtained based upon which research was carried out.

Solar Energy had abysmally low number of filings even lower grant percentage, wind energy had a quite healthy number of applications with a much healthier grant percentage. However, Indian R&D is present in solar, it is virtually absent in the Wind energy sector which is a cause of concern.

Solar Energy Inventions are originating from Europe and US jurisdictions. Wind Energy is originating from Germany and Denmark Jurisdictions. It has been seen that US has been finicky in its approach, as seen in the latest trade spat between India and US, therefore, while US could be a good partner with India, it is not recommended that India should form any sort of strategic alliance in terms of PPH model with US.

India should target Danish companies Vestas Wind Systems A/S and LM Glasfiber A/S along with deliberations with Danish government for Wind energy technology. India could further approach Germany and target companies like Siemens, Suzlon and Senvion. For solar thermal Germany could be a good partner and for PVs China, Japan and S. Korea with companies like LG, Samsung and Hyundai could be good partners. No complementary research is available in field of ESTs in India as per qualitative analysis of search results. Leverages shall have to be derived from elsewhere.

Leverages India could use are Space technology, Trade, PPH, etc. PPH particularly could include a clause wherein ESTs technology transfer and diffusion are a pre-condition for expedited examination of the patents. The diffusion could be done using Joint Venture or PPP model of execution of projects

6. CONCLUSION

ABSTRACT

IPRs, in particular Patents, can be hurdle or opportunity based on the situation. Integrated factors other than strictness of Patent Regime are also important in Diffusion of ESTs which have been discussed in detail in the present research. International Legal framework plays a crucial role in ESTs diffusion into India. Major legal frameworks relevant for present research include Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1883; Patent Cooperation Treaty, 1970; WTO framework; TRIPS; UNFCCC; WIPO Green and SDGs. Policy and Legal framework of India are also closely intertwined with diffusion of ESTs, their relationship is discussed in the present research. Policy related to climate change and renewable energy is also discussed. In Indian Legal Dimension, Strict Criteria of Patentability, Compulsory Licensing, Patent Prosecution Highway, Commercial Working Data and Renewable Energy is discussed. Thereafter, detailed empirical research is carried out wherein, search query is determined for wind and solar power generation technologies, yearly trends are studied, and nationality of applicants are determined. Towards the end of this research, summary of the research work carried out has been stated and suggestions have been described.

SUMMARY AND SUGGESTIONS

IPRs, specifically patents, are usually anti-competitive which is not good for industry. But they also provide for an opportunity for licensing-based or investment-based diffusion of technology by transfer of skill, expertise and trade secrets. Patenting regime works with other integrated factors to affect the diffusion of ESTs. Most of these factors can be change into favorable factors by India but the change is going to be extremely slow as most of these factors are that of relating to physical, financial, industrial and political infrastructure. Paris Treaty and PCT are crucial for retaining the priority when filing applications in multiple jurisdictions. Trade, WTO, and TRIPS play an intricate role as well. TRIPS under WTO framework enforces national treatment for Patents from other jurisdictions. WTO aims to lower direct and indirect barriers of trade. UNFCCC envisions diffusion of ESTs to achieve Climate Change objective. Diffusion of ESTs is going to help in making significant advances in the various SDGs.

The suggestion based on this chapter emanates from the idea of WIPO Green. While achievement of WIPO Green has been extremely limited, but it is a big step in right direction. After an extensive research on WIPO Green, the present research was unable to find a single fault in the WIPO Green Concept. WIPO Green is a sort of online marketplace wherein EST seekers post their needs, patentee upload the basic info on their technology which they are willing to collaborate or license the technology. The WIPO Green focusses on Green startups. India should take active participation in the WIPO Green. Further India could collaborate with the partners of WIPO Green to start an Indian chapter of the parent WIPO Green for better diffusion of ESTs into India.

Diffusion of ESTs to India is intricately related to Policy of Indian government, Indian Patent laws, Renewable Energy related laws and Renewable Energy related policy. NAPCC, 2008 created 8 missions to mitigate and adapt to the climate change. NAPCC was a trigger for many other policies including RPOs as part of Electricity Generation and Distribution systems.

Patents have a very strict criteria of Inventive Step. Further, Indian Patent Laws are in line with the TRIPS as a whole and specific its Article 27. Non-Patentability criteria mentioned in the Section 3 and 4 read with section 2(1) (j) and 2(1) (ja) makes sure that only Bona fide invention are granted patents. While Compulsory Licensing and/or inclusion of ESTs into Section 3 has been argued by some scholars as a way of boosting India's renewable energy equipment manufacturing sector, the present research argues against it.

While there are many critics of JPPH, the present research argue that it is well thought out move. The present research further suggests PPH as a mechanism of leveraging ESTs diffusion into India, more about which is discussed in summary and suggestions of Chapter 5. The present research criticizes Draft Amendment of Patent Rules, 2019 which liberalizes Form 27 requirements and dilutes requirement of disclosure of information regarding commercial working of the patent after the grant. The said amendment moves in the direction of lesser transparency which is never a good idea. It is argued that while this information is a motivator for inventor to commercial work an invention as failure to do so may attract Compulsory Licensing, another use of such data is increased competition in the market as licensing information, worth of invention worked is disclosed which is closely monitored by all the stakeholders.

RPOs have a significant effect on Renewable Energy production. RPOs cater to the larger public interest which shall prevail over the interests of the industry. Intermittency is a big shortcoming of the renewable energy. Unless energy storage systems like EnergyVault's concrete storage system, fuel cell or solar to ethanol, etc. are made practical and cost effective, intermittency will remain an issue. Flexibility mechanisms are one method to overcome the issue of intermittency examples of which have been described in detail in the chapter. Solar rooftop based on net metering and smart grid is a new age technique which can be used under the SPIN scheme to improve EST implementation. Integrated models and hybrid renewable systems could be another way forward.

Hybrid renewables systems, in an embodiment, includes solar thermal, solar pv and wind turbine which can be used simultaneously or alternatively based on the demand at a particular point of time.

Patent Search is an important tool, inter alia, for researchers, patent seekers and license seekers. Importance of good database cannot be underestimated. A good patent search database enables Examiners to prepare a good patentability report which could avoid post grant blushes to the Controller, or could provide crucial information to Researchers by which they can focus on which field should they research more on.

Characterized in That is a phrase generally used in Independent claims, wherein anything mentioned before such phrase is an invention which is already well known. Therefore, it is hereby suggested that Indian R&D Institutions should first try to innovate and work upon the technologies by discovering such prior arts.

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Solar Energy Inventions are originating from Europe and US jurisdictions. Wind Energy is originating from Germany and Denmark Jurisdictions. It has been seen that US has been finicky in its approach, as seen in the latest trade spat between India and US, therefore, while US could be a good partner with India, it is not recommended that India should form any sort of strategic alliance in terms of PPH model with US.

India should target Danish companies Vestas Wind Systems A/S and LM Glasfiber A/S along with deliberations with Danish government for Wind energy technology. India could further approach Germany and target companies like Siemens, Suzlon and Senvion. For solar thermal Germany could be a good partner and for PVs China, Japan and S. Korea with companies like LG, Samsung and Hyundai could be good partners. No complementary research is available in field of ESTs in India as per qualitative analysis of search results. Leverages shall have to be derived from elsewhere.

Leverages India could use are Space technology, Trade, PPH, etc. PPH particularly could include a clause wherein ESTs technology transfer and diffusion are a pre-condition for expedited examination of the patents. The diffusion could be done using Joint Venture or PPP model of execution of projects.

FINAL SUGGESTIONS

Strategies that can be adopted policy makers of India for increasing Diffusion of ESTs into India:

- Joint Venture based on research work on Patent Search as suggested above.
- Incorporating, Investment Mechanism into Patent act wherein expedited examination is granted to companies investing in manufacturing of EST equipment in India.
- Strategic Partnerships with Germany, Denmark, Japan and South Korea.
- Focus on funding domestic R&D.
- Technology exchange – leveraging ISROs space technology and services.
- Collaborative R&D with developed countries' private or public institutions.

- Expedited Process of granting patent if Technology Transfer via Joint Venture mechanism is found feasible.
- Commercial Working Data to be made more transparent.
- Improved Classification and IPC implementation in inPASS in line with IPC Green inventory. India should become a signatory to the Strasbourg Agreement.
- Collaboration with partners of WIPO Green. Opening a separate Indian chapter of WIPO Green.
- Special tagging of ESTs in patent database i.e. inPASS wherein all ESTs get a green tag and could be easily identifiable by way of a filter-based search.
- Making Dirty technologies costlier by imposition of Pollution tax mechanisms. Impending adoption of Bharat Stage 6 norms for diesel has already resulted into automobile manufacturers shifting their focus of R&D on less polluting fuel options from diesel.

While our research has been based on the *quantity* of granted patents and number of applications. It is crucial to note that **Qualitative Aspect** of the patents should not be ignored.

- The Solar PV manufacturing is done majorly in 4 stages¹³⁰:
 - Firstly, extracting Silicon from its natural state i.e. Silicates of the sand.
 - Secondly, producing high quality ingots of Silicon, referred to as Solar grade Silicon ingots from Silicon manufactured in previous step.
 - Thirdly, manufacturing thin slices of semiconductors termed as Solar wafers from Solar grade Silicon ingots.
 - Fourthly and lastly, assembling the Solar PV modules.
- “The capital expenditure and technical know-how needed for these processes decreases from the first item to the last, i.e. silicon production is more capital-intensive than module assembly.”¹³¹ Therefore, to build a good manufacturing ecosystem for Solar equipment, India needs to focus on all the four stages and putting more focus on the first ones.
- It is possible that in the supply chains certain entities hold patents on such key technology, let us say for example in first stage of Solar manufacturing, wherein without such a license of such key patented technology it would be impossible to become independent of imports.
- The present researcher, therefore, takes liberty in coining a term called **keystone patents**. Keystone is a stone in an arch type stone bridge which takes the least burden of the loads and at the same time in absence of such a stone, the entire bridge collapses. Herein, a keystone patent in manufacturing supply chain could become a bottleneck in building the manufacturing capacity in a particular sector.
- While the present research has vehemently argued against Compulsory licensing, a solution to such keystone patented technologies could lie in issuing compulsory licenses on Fair Reasonable And Non Discriminatory or simply FRAND terms in line with the

¹³⁰ Santosh Mehrotra, *India needs a solar manufacturing strategy*, THE HINDU, <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/india-needs-a-solar-manufacturing-strategy/article27526839.ece>.

¹³¹ *Ibid.*

practices adopted for the 4G telecom sector wherein FRAND licenses were issued after LTE was adopted as industry standard over Wi-MAX for 4G telecom services.

- The future research could focus on identifying such keystone patents and thereby finding the appropriate redressal mechanism to ensure smooth ESTs diffusion into India.

Long term steps that can be adopted policy makers of India for increasing Diffusion of ESTs into India:

- Improving economic and physical Infrastructure facilities.
- Improving Governance including regulatory framework.
- Improved dispute resolution specially for ESTs. Latest decision of Ministry of New and Renewable Energy to set up a three-member dispute resolution committee for solar and wind projects implemented through/by Solar Energy Corporation of India or National Thermal Power Corporation Limited¹³² is a step in the right direction in this regard.
- Strengthening of R&D and educational Institutions.
- Skill Development to improve the quality of labor.
- More streamlined, harmonious, and quick regulatory approvals.
- Improving Balance of trade to get more leverage.
- Building Technical and Organizational capacity to absorb the ESTs arriving in India quickly.
- Using Merger and Acquisitions as a tool of leveraging the transfers. Acquiring small foreign companies that have good command on ESTs.
- Improving industrial capacity and industrial supply chain. Patent is a type of Industrial IPR. It has been seen that significant portion of the Patents originate from the nations with well-established industries. This is so, because the technical problems are witnessed only while manufacturing a particular product repeatedly. Patents are inherently advancements over existing prior arts which solve a technical problem. Therefore, building Industrial capacity leads to augmentation of innovation and diffusion capabilities of a nation.

¹³² PTI, *MNRE to set up dispute resolution panel for solar, wind projects implemented by SECI, NTPC*, TIMES OF INDIA, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/mnre-to-set-up-dispute-resolution-panel-for-solar-wind-projects-implemented-by-seci-ntpc/articleshow/69857011.cms>.

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